

Relationships Between Livestock
Production and Ambient Water Quality in
the Sandusky Basin

Final Grant Report

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Executive Summary

When addressing water quality issues at the watershed level, accurate problem identification is a critical first step. Early in problem identification, it is necessary to determine whether the problem affects ambient water quality within the streams and rivers of the watershed, or whether the problem is associated with downstream waters that receive pollutant loading from the watershed. In our local context, are the problems in the Sandusky River and its tributaries, or are they in Sandusky Bay and Lake Erie?

In this project, we investigated the degree to which current livestock operations in a six county area, primarily within the Sandusky River Watershed, are impacting ambient water quality in the streams and rivers of the area. The sampling approach involved a low flow, synoptic survey. Personnel from local soil and water conservation districts and the Natural Resource Conservation Service organized county committees to select sampling stations. Stations either bracketed (upstream and downstream) likely sources of livestock contamination, or were located at the mouths of smaller watersheds with either extensive or minimal livestock production. Stations were also selected that bracketed human sources of nutrients, such as areas having extensive septic tanks or package plants. Ninety-three stations were selected. Each station was visited twice during low flow conditions in October 1996 or September/October 1997. The impacts we investigated included elevated nutrient concentrations and depleted oxygen concentrations.

While elevated nutrients were evident at some stations downstream from livestock sources, on average livestock impacted stations were not significantly different than their controls. In contrast, nutrient concentrations were significantly higher at stations downstream from human sources than nutrient concentrations were significantly higher at stations downstream from human sources than at their upstream controls. Also, total phosphorus and nitrate concentrations were significantly higher downstream from human sources than downstream from livestock sources. Oxygen concentrations were low downstream from some livestock impacted stations, as well as some human impacted stations. However, average oxygen concentrations were not significantly different at downstream stations than at upstream controls for both livestock and human sources.

The above observations reflect a major and important difference between livestock and human sources. Human sources are characterized by continuous discharges of water and wastes. As stream flows become low, human wastes continue to find their way into streams. In contrast, most, but not all, livestock sources require rainfall to wash pollutants into streams. Thus the impacts of livestock are more likely to be present as part of ambient stream water quality during high flow periods and as part of the overall loading of pollutants to downstream receiving waters. During rainfall events, pollutants from other nonpoint sources, such as fertilized cropland, urban runoff, and combined sewer overflows also enter streams. Consequently, during rainfall conditions, when other nonpoint sources are contributing pollutants, it may be difficult to identify the extent of livestock contributions to the overall nutrient export from the watershed.

Storm runoff conditions in streams are present for a relatively small proportion of time in comparison to non-runoff conditions of medium and low flows. Consequently, human sources of pollutants may be more important than livestock sources in terms of impacts on ambient water quality in streams. Previous and ongoing monitoring in the Sandusky and neighboring rivers documents that agricultural sources dominate total loading of nutrients and sediments into Lake Erie and Sandusky Bay. Assessment of livestock's contribution to agricultural loading into Lake Erie can be accomplished through development of nutrient budgets for the contributing watersheds. The contributions of livestock to total nutrient loading, together with spills of concentrated livestock wastes, appear to represent the greatest water quality threats posed by livestock production in this region.

INTRODUCTION

One of the current trends in agriculture is the growth of large, confined livestock feeding operations for the production of meat, eggs and milk. Such operations have the potential to adversely impact water resources in a variety of ways. Runoff of oxygen consuming wastes, such as dissolved and particulate organic matter or ammonia, can lower oxygen concentrations in the water. Depleted dissolved oxygen can result in fish kills and alter the types of organisms that make up stream bottom communities. Manure-derived nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus containing compounds, can be loaded into streams during runoff events, leading to eutrophication of downstream lakes, estuaries, and nearshore zones. Such nutrients can also be delivered into streams during low flow conditions, adversely impacting ambient water quality in the streams themselves. Livestock manure can also be the source of disease causing microorganisms, such as *Cryptosporidium* or *Giardia*.

Various approaches to water quality monitoring are required to document the above types of adverse water quality impacts. Usually, the delivery of oxygen consuming wastes from livestock operations into streams and rivers is intermittent. Leaks or spills may occur when manure is being applied or at other times. Waste holding ponds may overflow due to rainfall events or flooding, thereby delivering concentrated wastes into surface waters. Surface applied manure may be carried into streams or rivers during rainfall or snowmelt events. Since the entry of the oxygen consuming materials is intermittent, monitoring of depleted oxygen levels in streams and rivers due to livestock wastes is difficult. Often, fish kills are the first sign of oxygen problems, and oxygen measurements become part of the fish kill investigation. Sometimes, continuous oxygen monitors may be installed in vulnerable locations so that intermittent episodes of low dissolved oxygen can be detected. Otherwise, spot checks of dissolved oxygen, such as those conducted as part of synoptic surveys, may reveal problems. Diurnal fluctuations in dissolved oxygen associated with the photosynthetic cycle may complicate interpretation of this type of oxygen measurement.

Assessing impacts of livestock on nutrient loading to downstream receiving waters requires the measurement of both stream flows and nutrient concentrations. Generally, nutrient loading rates are highest during runoff events. Nutrient loading is the product of stream flow and nutrient concentrations and both of these change significantly during runoff events. Consequently, efforts to accurately measure nutrient loading in streams require continuous measurements of discharge and automatic sampling of water for subsequent chemical measurements. Because such studies require analysis of many samples, studies of nutrient loading in streams are costly, and often exceed the monitoring budget of local projects. Typically, such studies would only be done at a small number of locations in a watershed.

Where livestock operations result in a steady introduction of nutrients into streams, low flow, synoptic studies may be used to locate and quantify the resulting ambient water quality problems. Under conditions of low flow, minimal quantities of water are present in the streams to dilute incoming wastes, and, consequently, nutrient concentrations may be very high. If the rates of nutrient input and stream flows are both relatively constant, the resulting nutrient concentrations will be relatively constant at a given location. Synoptic collections, which involve near simultaneous sample collections at multiple locations in a watershed, provide an effective way to identify this type of problem.

Problems associated with the introduction of disease-causing microorganisms into streams can occur during any of the above situations -- spills, high flow runoff, and low flow discharge into streams. Sampling and microbiological testing would have to be done during all of these times to characterize impacts of livestock on microbiological water

quality. It should be noted that not all pathological microorganisms originate directly from the animal wastes. Elevated inorganic nutrients in receiving waters can stimulate the growth of various types of algae, including some forms which are toxic to humans, fish or shellfish.

The objectives of this study were to evaluate the extent to which livestock operations were leading to ambient water quality problems in streams and rivers of a six county area in north central Ohio. Most of the sampling occurred within the Sandusky River watershed. Specifically, we focused on the question of possible nutrient elevation in streams during low and medium flows. Since human wastes from septic tanks, package plants and sewage treatment plants can also lead to elevated nutrient concentrations during low flow conditions, we also took measurements at locations in the stream where such impacts were thought to occur. Dissolved oxygen measurements were also taken at the time of sample collection to examine possible dissolved oxygen problems associated with both livestock or human wastes entering the streams.

METHODS

Site Selection

Representatives of local soil and water conservation districts and the Natural Resource Conservation Service were requested to aid in the selection of sampling locations for each of six counties. Guidelines for site selection for the synoptic survey were developed by staff of the Heidelberg College Water Quality Laboratory (WQL) and provided to the county representatives (see Appendix 1). The guidelines included selection of sites upstream and downstream from possible livestock sources along a stream, sites on streams draining watersheds having greatly differing amounts of livestock related nutrient sources. Selection of sites upstream and downstream from possible human sources were also recommended. A total of 93 sites were selected in the six counties.

The types of sites, along with the coding used to identify sites are summarized in Table 1. Upstream sites or control watersheds are coded by x.0 designations while downstream sites or impacted watersheds are coded by x.2 designations. The "x" indicates the particular type of pollutant source (feedlots, manure applications, septic tanks, etc.). The number of sites selected for each type and the number of samples collected for each type is also shown in Table 1. Insufficient information was available to classify several of the sites. Samples were collected at those sites and the data are included in the appendix.

For each county, the sites were numbered. County maps of the locations of the collection sites are shown in Appendix 2. This appendix also contains a description of the road/bridge location for each site, its coding, and a brief rationale for its selection, as provided by the county representatives.

Field Measurements and Sample Collection

WQL staff visited each site during low flow conditions in the fall of 1996 and 1997. Oxygen and temperature measurements were taken at each site, using a YSI oxygen meter calibrated against air. The date and time of sample collection was recorded in field notebooks, along with any qualitative observations at individual stations that might aid in data interpretation.

Table 1. Site type codes for various potential pollutant sources.

Condition or potential pollutant source	Position	Site Type Code	number of sites selected	number of samples collected
Sewage treatment plant	Upstream	1.0	7	13
	Downstream	1.2	8	12
Septic tanks/package plants	Upstream	2.0	10	19
	Downstream	2.2	13	26
Feedlot adjacent to stream/animal access to stream	Upstream	3.0	7	13
	Downstream	3.2	10	19
Small streams, adjacent fields with high manure	Upstream	4.0	6	12
	Downstream	4.2	7	14
Small watersheds with minimal application of manure		5.0	5	7
Small watershed with heavy application of manure		5.2	5	10
Watersheds with low animal densities		6.0	5	8
Watersheds with high animal densities		6.2	2	4
Streams having adjacent fields receiving sludge	Upstream	7.0	1	2
	Downstream	7.2	1	2
Baseline watersheds		8.0	4	7

At each station, water samples were collected for delivery to the WQL's analytical laboratories. Samples were collected either by lowering a bucket from the bridge at the collection site, or by wading into the stream. Samples were collected from the portion of the stream cross section having the greatest flow. Samples were transferred from the bucket to one-liter, labeled sample bottles. At least one field replicate was collected for every 10 stations. Samples were delivered to the laboratory on the same day they were collected. At some locations, insufficient water was present to allow sample collection. As illustrated in Table 1, not all sites are represented by samples from both years of the project.

Laboratory Analyses

The analytical methods used by the WQL are listed in Table 2. Automated techniques are used for all of the colorimetric procedures. The abbreviations used for each parameter are also shown in Table 2. The agreement between field replicate samples for synoptic surveys conducted by the WQL are shown in Appendix 3.

Table 2. Analytical methods used by the Water Quality Laboratory at Heidelberg College.

Parameter	Equipment	Method Reference*
1. Total Phosphorus (TP)	Technicon AAI	EPA Method 365.3
2. Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN)	Technicon AAI	EPA Method 351.2
3. Nitrate plus nitrate nitrogen (NO ₂)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 353.2
4. Nitrite nitrogen (NO ₂)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 353.2
5. Ammonia nitrogen (NH ₃)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 350.1
6. Chloride (Cl)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 325.2
7. Soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 365.3
8. Sulfate (SO ₄)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 375.2
9. Silica (SiO ₂)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 370.1
10. Specific Conductance (Cond)	Technicon TRAACs	EPA Method 120.1
11. Suspended Sediment (SS)	Mettler Balances	EPA Method 160.2

*Methods for Analysis of Water and Wastes, EPA 600/4-79-020, Cincinnati, OH, 1979

RESULTS

A total of 178 samples were collected and analyzed as part of this study. For most of the stations, samples were collected in both 1996 and 1997. However, for some stations, low water levels at the time of collection prevented collection of samples both years.

All of the results of the field measurements and the laboratory analyses are shown in Appendix 2. The data are presented by county, along with a station map and description of the sampling sites for each county.

Range of Analytical Results

The range of analytical results for the 178 samples are shown in the form of concentration exceedency curves for each parameter (Figures 1-6). In these graphs, the percentage of the samples having concentrations that exceed various levels are shown. Thus for ammonia (Figure 1), approximately 10% of the samples have concentrations exceeding 1.0 mg/L.

The concentration exceedency graphs indicate that for most parameters, a small number of samples have high concentrations, while the large majority of samples have low concentrations. This pattern is particularly evident for ammonia, soluble phosphorus, total phosphorus, chloride and conductivity (Figures 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6). For nitrate (Figure 2), the graph does not drop off so quickly, and more samples have intermediate values.

Characteristics of Sites with High Nutrient Concentrations

In Tables 3-6, the samples with the highest concentrations of nutrients or lowest dissolved oxygen are identified by location, and their site types are listed. In Table 3, locations of samples with high ammonia-nitrogen and high nitrate-nitrogen are shown. Of the 20 samples with the highest ammonia concentrations, 14 fell in a downstream category (i.e., downstream from either livestock or human input sources (x.2)) Of these 14, nine were downstream from potential human sources and five were downstream from potential livestock sources. Possible sources of high ammonia at the upstream locations (x.0) are unknown.

Figure 1. Concentration exceedency curve for ammonia-N in low flow synoptic surveys.

Figure 2. Concentration exceedency curve for nitrate-N in low flow synoptic surveys.

Figure 3. Concentration exceedency curve for soluble reactive phosphorus in low flow synoptic surveys.

Figure 4. Concentration exceedency curve for total phosphorus in low flow synoptic surveys.

Figure 5. Concentration exceedency curve for chloride in low flow synoptic surveys.

Figure 6. Concentration exceedency curve for conductivity in low flow synoptic surveys.

Table 3. Stations with highest concentrations of ammonia and nitrate nitrogen.

County/ Station #	Site Type	NH3 (mg/L)	Rank	County/ Station #	Site Type	NO23 (mg/L)	Rank
Hardin #7	2.2	24.64	1	Crawford #13	3.0	7.79	1
Hardin #10	5.2	7.41	2	Crawford #13	3.0	7.08	2
Wyandot #11	2.2	6.90	3	Wyandot #15	4.0	6.40	3
Seneca #15	3.2	5.71	4	Crawford #4	1.2	5.71	4
Wyandot #11	2.2	5.31	5	Crawford #12	3.2	5.70	5
Crawford #9	5.2	5.30	6	Marion #9	2.2	5.54	6
Crawford #14	2.2	4.83	7	Sandusky #3	2.0	5.46	7
Crawford #14	2.2	3.88	8	Sandusky #9	2.2	5.26	8
Seneca #2	4.0	3.26	9	Crawford #12	3.2	5.24	9
Hardin #12	1.2	2.54	10	Wyandot #15	4.0	5.08	10
Marion #7	2.2	2.12	11	Marion #10		5.02	11
Crawford #9	5.2	1.71	12	Crawford #4	1.2	4.54	12
Sandusky #3	2.0	1.56	13	Wyandot #14	4.2	3.69	13
Sandusky #6	7.0	1.46	14	Seneca #17	2.2	3.41	14
Sandusky #4	2.2	1.36	15	Seneca #17	2.2	3.33	15
Sandusky #6	7.0	1.32	16	Seneca #18	3.2	3.31	16
Wyandot #7	4.0	1.22	17	Seneca #18	3.2	3.30	17
Sandusky #15	4.2	1.20	18	Seneca #17A	2.2	3.28	18
Sandusky #14	4.0	1.14	19	Seneca #19	3.0	2.99	19
Sandusky #4	2.2	1.02	20	Seneca #12	2.0	2.73	20
Marion #10		0.93	21	Hardin #7	2.2	2.70	21
Seneca #4	1.2	0.66	22	Seneca #13	3.2	2.64	22
Wyandot #5	3.0	0.56	23	Seneca #11	2.2	2.61	23
Sandusky #14	4.0	0.32	24	Seneca #20	2.2	2.59	24
Wyandot #8	3.0	0.32	25	Seneca #20	2.2	2.58	25
Wyandot #7	4.0	0.29	26	Seneca #21	2.0	2.47	26
Marion #12	2.0	0.28	27	Wyandot #5	3.0	2.38	27
Wyandot #10	2.0	0.28	28	Hardin #12	1.2	2.37	28
Crawford #7	1.0	0.27	29	Crawford #14	2.2	2.23	29
Hardin #5	4.0	0.25	30	Seneca #22A	1.2	2.22	30
Seneca #17	2.2	0.24	31	Crawford #9	5.2	2.18	31
Hardin #7	2.2	0.24	32	Crawford #14	2.2	2.16	32
Wyandot #4	3.2	0.24	33	Sandusky #4	2.2	2.05	33
Seneca #1	5.0	0.23	34	Sandusky #6	7.0	2.05	34
Wyandot #4	3.2	0.21	35	Marion #9	2.2	2.02	35
Sandusky #3	2.0	0.20	36	Hardin #12	1.2	2.02	36
Crawford #10	3.2	0.18	37	Marion #11	2.2	1.99	37
Seneca #23	1.0	0.17	38	Seneca #23	1.0	1.91	38
Crawford #4	1.2	0.16	39	Wyandot #14	4.2	1.89	39
Marion #8	2.0	0.16	40	Seneca #4	1.2	1.80	40

Table 4. Stations with highest concentrations of soluble reactive phosphorus and total phosphorus.

County/ Station #	Site Type	SRP (mg/L)	Rank	County/ Station #	Site Type	TP (mg/L)	Rank
Hardin #10	5.2	3.120	1	Crawford #9	5.2	4.341	1
Hardin #7	2.2	2.600	2	Hardin #10	5.2	3.721	2
Crawford #9	5.2	2.120	3	Marion #10		3.319	3
Marion #10		1.700	4	Hardin #7	2.2	2.406	4
Crawford #9	5.2	1.560	5	Crawford #9	5.2	1.764	5
Wyandot #11	2.2	1.240	6	Wyandot #11	2.2	1.504	6
Crawford #14	2.2	1.136	7	Crawford #14	2.2	1.365	7
Crawford #13	3.0	1.031	8	Sandusky #9	2.2	1.304	8
Sandusky #9	2.2	0.910	9	Crawford #13	3.0	1.108	9
Crawford #13	3.0	0.811	10	Crawford #14	2.2	1.011	10
Crawford #14	2.2	0.768	11	Crawford #13	3.0	0.964	11
Crawford #12	3.2	0.687	12	Wyandot #11	2.2	0.827	12
Wyandot #11	2.2	0.557	13	Marion #1	3.2	0.796	13
Hardin #12	1.2	0.540	14	Hardin #12	1.2	0.784	14
Crawford #12	3.2	0.514	15	Crawford #12	3.2	0.774	15
Crawford #4	1.2	0.413	16	Crawford #12	3.2	0.702	16
Seneca #15	3.2	0.412	17	Seneca #15	3.2	0.661	17
Marion #7	2.2	0.369	18	Wyandot #5	3.0	0.641	18
Wyandot #5	3.0	0.346	19	Wyandot #7	4.0	0.615	19
Marion #1	3.2	0.338	20	Sandusky #6	7.0	0.572	20
Sandusky #6	7.0	0.313	21	Marion #7	2.2	0.517	21
Wyandot #7	4.0	0.295	22	Crawford #4	1.2	0.512	22
Hardin #12	1.2	0.286	23	Wyandot #13	2.2	0.477	23
Seneca #2	4.0	0.260	24	Seneca #4	1.2	0.459	24
Sandusky #3	2.0	0.255	25	Marion #9	2.2	0.445	25
Wyandot #14	4.2	0.248	26	Wyandot #6	4.2	0.417	26
Seneca #4	1.2	0.214	27	Hardin #12	1.2	0.398	27
Marion #9	2.2	0.210	28	Sandusky #14	4.0	0.395	28
Sandusky #4	2.2	0.206	29	Wyandot #7	4.0	0.376	29
Wyandot #7	4.0	0.184	30	Sandusky #15	4.2	0.375	30
Hardin #9	2.0	0.166	31	Wyandot #14	4.2	0.374	31
Sandusky #15	4.2	0.163	32	Sandusky #4	2.2	0.364	32
Sandusky #4	2.2	0.159	33	Hardin #9	2.0	0.359	33
Marion #8	2.0	0.137	34	Sandusky #4	2.2	0.314	34
Sandusky #12	1.2	0.127	35	Hardin #3	5.2	0.300	35
Wyandot #12	2.0	0.119	36	Sandusky #6	7.0	0.293	36
Marion #9	2.2	0.117	37	Wyandot #12	2.0	0.258	37
Marion #11	2.2	0.113	38	Marion #9	2.2	0.255	38
Sandusky #14	4.0	0.111	39	Seneca #22		0.247	39
Hardin #8	5.0	0.109	40	Marion #11	2.2	0.217	40
Hardin #5	4.0	0.103	41	Hardin #2	1.2	0.216	41

Table 5. Stations with highest concentrations of chloride and conductivity.

County/ Station #	Site Type	Chloride (mg/L)	Rank	County/ Station #	Site Type	Cond. (µmhos)	Rank
Wyandot #8	3.0	2030.0	1	Sandusky #4	2.2	13510	1
Seneca #15	3.2	840.3	2	Sandusky #6	7.0	10700	2
Sandusky #4	2.2	840.0	3	Sandusky #3	2.0	10050	3
Sandusky #4	2.2	698.7	4	Sandusky #7	7.2	9920	4
Hardin #10	5.2	601.7	5	Wyandot #8	3.0	6580	5
Sandusky #6	7.0	586.3	6	Seneca #15	3.2	4450	6
Sandusky #3	2.0	524.2	7	Hardin #10	5.2	4030	7
Crawford #9	5.2	437.3	8	Sandusky #4	2.2	3540	8
Seneca #2	4.0	406.8	9	Seneca #2	4.0	3080	9
Marion #9	2.2	331.4	10	Sandusky #5	8.0	2920	10
Sandusky #7	7.2	310.2	11	Sandusky #5	8.0	2310	11
Sandusky #3	2.0	305.9	12	Wyandot #13	2.2	2120	12
Crawford #14	2.2	239.0	13	Wyandot #5	3.0	2070	13
Wyandot #5	3.0	208.6	14	Crawford #9	5.2	2020	14
Crawford #14	2.2	203.5	15	Wyandot #11	2.2	1895	15
Marion #7	2.2	195.9	16	Sandusky #14	4.0	1725	16
Sandusky #6	7.0	184.7	17	Wyandot #11	2.2	1717	17
Sandusky #14	4.0	174.6	18	Sandusky #3	2.0	1672	18
Sandusky #9	2.2	168.2	19	Marion #9	2.2	1631	19
Marion #9	2.2	167.5	20	Sandusky #11	1.0	1580	20
Hardin #9	2.0	155.6	21	Wyandot #12	2.0	1546	21
Wyandot #10	2.0	155.5	22	Crawford #14	2.2	1462	22
Sandusky #15	4.2	155.0	23	Crawford #14	2.2	1451	23
Wyandot #11	2.2	149.8	24	Wyandot #13	2.2	1442	24
Wyandot #13	2.2	145.9	25	Sandusky #15	4.2	1413	25
Sandusky #11	1.0	143.9	26	Marion #9	2.2	1387	26
Wyandot #11	2.2	139.8	27	Crawford #9	5.2	1318	27
Wyandot #10	2.0	137.3	28	Sandusky #9	2.2	1317	28
Sandusky #13	6.0	126.4	29	Sandusky #6	7.0	1316	29
Sandusky #7	7.2	125.8	30	Hardin #7	2.2	1301	30
Wyandot #6	4.2	124.4	31	Wyandot #12	2.0	1243	31
Seneca #15	3.2	120.4	32	Wyandot #7	4.0	1226	32
Seneca #4	1.2	118.5	33	Hardin #9	2.0	1194	33
Wyandot #9	3.2	118.1	34	Sandusky #11	1.0	1191	34
Seneca #16	3.0	110.0	35	Crawford #15	5.0	1186	35
Crawford #9	5.2	108.0	36	Sandusky #12	1.2	1182	36
Sandusky #12	1.2	107.1	37	Wyandot #10	2.0	1180	37
Sandusky #11	1.0	106.7	38	Wyandot #14	4.2	1152	38
Seneca #3	8.0	105.4	39	Wyandot #6	4.2	1129	39
Marion #8	2.0	102.1	40	Wyandot #10	2.0	1115	40

Table 6. Stations with highest concentrations of ammonia and nitrate nitrogen.

County/ Location	Site Type	Date	Time	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	Rank
Hardin #10	5.2	971010	1139	0.0	1
Marion #1	3.2	961026	1606	0.7	2
Wyandot #13	2.2	971010	1444	1.0	3
Marion #2	3.2	961026	1552	1.3	4
Crawford #9	5.2	961017	1053	1.3	5
Hardin #12	1.2	971010	1158	1.7	6
Hardin #3	5.2	971010	1102	2.0	7
Seneca #2	4.0	961015	1522	2.6	8
Seneca #4	1.2	970916	0948	2.7	9
Crawford #6	4.2	961017	0929	2.8	10
Hardin #13	1.0	971010	1214	2.9	11
Hardin #9	2.0	970905	1240	2.9	12
Wyandot #5	3.0	971010	1028	2.9	13
Sandusky #9	2.2	961015	0937	3.0	14
Sandusky #8	2.0	961015	0946	3.1	15
Crawford #3	5.2	970918	0944	3.2	16
Crawford #9	5.2	970918	1059	3.2	17
Crawford #2	6.2	961017	1156	3.2	18
Hardin #2	1.2	971010	1326	3.3	19
Marion #8	2.0	970918	1423	3.3	20
Wyandot #6	4.2	971010	1045	3.3	21
Sandusky #6	7.0	961015	1159	3.4	22
Wyandot #2	1.0	971010	0917	3.5	23
Marion #7	2.2	970918	1426	3.5	24
Seneca #1	5.0	970916	1022	3.5	25
Hardin #1	1.0	971010	1316	4.0	26
Wyandot #4	3.2	971010	1019	4.4	27
Hardin #7	2.2	971010	1121	4.5	28
Hardin #11	6.0	970905	1230	4.6	29
Crawford #14	2.2	961017	1017	4.6	30
Crawford #6	4.2	970918	1244	4.7	31
Crawford #1	5.0	970918	0917	4.8	32
Wyandot #12	2.0	971010	1439	5.0	33
Crawford #14	2.2	970918	1137	5.0	34
Seneca #7	2.2	961015	1649	5.0	35
Crawford #4	1.2	961017	1127	5.1	36
Marion #8	2.0	961026	1503	5.2	37
Sandusky #6	7.0	970916	1258	5.2	38
Sandusky #12	1.2	961015	1059	5.2	39
Crawford #5	4.0	961017	0938	5.3	40

Of the 20 samples with the highest nitrate, 12 samples were from "downstream" sites (x.2). Seven of the 12 were downstream from potential human sources and five were downstream from livestock sources. The sources of high nitrate at the 7 "upstream" locations are unknown. Two of the "downstream" livestock samples (both from Crawford #12) were actually downstream from samples with even higher nitrate at the corresponding upstream station (Crawford #13). Thus the identified livestock sources between these sites may not have contributed to the elevated nitrate at the downstream location.

The data illustrate one of the characteristics of nitrogen forms in rivers. Samples with elevated ammonia generally do not have elevated nitrate. There is no overlap between the 20 samples with the highest ammonia and the twenty samples with the highest nitrate. When both ammonia and nitrate are present, the intermediate form of nitrogen (nitrite) is often present. In streams, ammonia is converted to nitrate with nitrite as an intermediate in the conversion. This conversion also requires dissolved oxygen, and is a source of the low dissolved oxygen that usually accompanies high ammonia concentrations. The three highest nitrite concentrations occurred in Hardin #7, Crawford #9 and Crawford #14. These samples all had high ammonia (top 20) and nitrate levels in the 21-40 ranking. Most modern sewage treatment plants convert ammonia to nitrate within the sewage treatment plant, to avoid both direct ammonia toxicity and depleted oxygen in the receiving waters.

Sixteen of the 20 samples with the highest soluble reactive phosphorus were at downstream locations (Table 4). Of these 16, nine were downstream from human sources and seven were downstream from livestock sources. Fourteen of the highest total phosphorus were at downstream sites while 5 were at upstream sites (Table 4). In these samples, there is a strong correlation between samples with high soluble phosphorus and high total phosphorus. Phosphorus from human and livestock point sources generally is composed primarily of soluble reactive phosphorus. Since the total phosphorus analysis includes response to soluble reactive phosphorus, in these samples the soluble reactive phosphorus will be a high percentage of the total phosphorus. Thus, for the 20 samples with the highest soluble phosphorus, 18 also ranked among the twenty highest total phosphorus. However, total phosphorus can be high when the soluble reactive phosphorus is low. During periods of high suspended sediment runoff from cropland erosion, high concentrations of total phosphorus occur, with most of the phosphorus adsorbed to sediment particles rather than as soluble reactive phosphorus. Samples where the soluble phosphorus is a high percentage of total phosphorus generally reflect either human or livestock wastes entering the stream nearby. Of the 20 highest soluble reactive phosphorus, 10 were also among the highest 20 ammonia samples.

Of the 20 samples with the highest chloride, 12 were at downstream sites and 8 were at upstream sites (Table 5). Of the 12 downstream sites, 8 were below potential human sources and 3 were below potential livestock sources. For conductivity, which is a measure of the total dissolved ion concentration, of the twenty highest sites, 10 were at downstream locations and 10 were at upstream locations (Table 5). Of the 10 downstream locations, 6 were below human sources and 3 were below livestock sources. Eight of the 20 highest chloride samples and 5 of the twenty highest conductivity samples were among the 20 highest soluble reactive phosphorus samples.

Characteristics of Sites with Low Oxygen Concentrations

In Table 6, sites with the lowest oxygen concentrations are listed. Oxygen concentrations below 5.0 mg/L represent a violation of warm water standards. Thirty-three of the dissolved oxygen measurements fell below 5 mg/L. Of the 20 samples with the lowest dissolved oxygen, 14 were at downstream locations and 6 were at upstream

stations. Of the 14 downstream stations, 9 were below livestock facilities and 5 were below sources of human wastes.

The time (military, 24 hour clock) of the sampling is also listed for each sample, so that possible influences of diurnal oxygen fluctuations can be assessed. Typically, diurnal oxygen fluctuations associated with daytime photosynthesis (oxygen production) and night time respiration (oxygen consumption) of plant communities result in minimum dissolved oxygen just before sunrise and maximum dissolved oxygen in late afternoon. Some of the samples with the lowest oxygen concentrations were collected near the noon hour and into the early afternoon. It is doubtful that the low dissolved oxygen at these sites can be attributed to diurnal oxygen fluctuations. Instead, it appears that oxygen consuming wastes are entering the streams. Further testing at some of these sites is warranted to determine more precisely the cause of the low dissolved oxygen.

Comparison of Livestock and Human Impacts

In Table 7, the average (mean) and median concentrations for each site type are shown along with the numbers of samples in each site type. Where upstream and downstream stations bracketed potential human sources, such as sewage treatment plants (1.0 versus 1.2) or septic tanks/package plants (2.0 vs 2.2), both average and median concentrations increased at the downstream stations for all cases, often by large amounts. These increases applied to ammonia, chloride, nitrate, soluble reactive phosphorus, total phosphorus and total Kjeldahl nitrogen.

Where upstream and downstream sources bracketed potential livestock sources (3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 versus 3.2, 4.2, 5.2, 6.2), and for the above 6 chemicals, increases at downstream sites were not always present. Average concentrations at downstream sites increased for 13 cases and decreased for 11 cases. The median concentrations at downstream sites increased for 13 cases, decreased for 9 cases and remained unchanged for 2 cases.

The highest average soluble reactive phosphorus, total phosphorus, and total Kjeldahl nitrogen occurred for site type 5.2 (downstream for watersheds with heavy application of manure). However, the median concentrations of soluble reactive phosphorus, total phosphorus and total Kjeldahl nitrogen at site type 5.2 were lower than the corresponding median values for site type 2.2 (downstream from septic tanks/package plants). For the majority of other parameters, the highest average and median values were downstream from human influences (1.2, 2.2).

In Table 8, the sites are lumped into 5 categories: upstream from potential human inputs, downstream from potential human inputs, upstream from potential livestock inputs, downstream from potential livestock inputs and reference watersheds (no obvious upstream sources of any type, other than row crop agriculture). This table clearly illustrates that under conditions of low flow, human sources of nutrients have larger impacts on stream nutrient levels than do livestock sources.

The lumped data are also presented as box and whisker plots in Figures 7-14. Interpretation of the box and whisker plots is illustrated in Figure 15. The concentration data for all parameters except oxygen were log transformed prior to plotting. The elevated nutrient concentrations downstream from human sources are clearly evident in these figures.

Table 7. Average (mean) and median concentrations by site type.

Site Type	Number of Samples	Statistic	Dis. Oxygen mg/L	Temperature degrees C	NH3 mg/L	CL mg/L	NO2 mg/L	NO23 mg/L	SIO2 mg/L	SO4 mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	COND µmhos	SS mg/L
1.0	13	average	6.5	17.2	0.065	51.1	0.007	0.33	4.15	149	0.025	0.090	0.59	873	14
		median	6.2	17.3	0.050	34.0	0.000	0.18	4.49	81	0.010	0.077	0.46	802	13
1.2	12	average	5.9	17.3	0.314	59.5	0.060	1.88	4.76	131	0.150	0.273	0.99	875	21
		median	5.8	18.1	0.062	49.6	0.015	1.74	4.45	85	0.072	0.194	0.72	931	13
2.0	19	average	8.3	17.8	0.165	104.7	0.032	0.97	6.29	153	0.050	0.124	0.78	1457	24
		median	8.1	18.2	0.080	56.4	0.010	0.40	6.25	93	0.019	0.095	0.77	966	12
2.2	26	average	7.0	16.9	1.972	156.9	0.113	1.79	7.42	202	0.348	0.489	2.27	1707	14
		median	6.3	17.7	0.080	86.2	0.055	1.80	7.58	92	0.092	0.215	0.89	1082	10
3.0	13	average	8.5	18.1	0.102	212.2	0.022	1.77	4.43	158	0.186	0.288	0.83	1304	24
		median	8.0	17.2	0.040	58.1	0.010	0.16	4.01	89	0.014	0.133	0.81	787	18
3.2	19	average	7.2	16.3	0.361	93.0	0.035	1.36	4.54	211	0.123	0.233	0.99	985	14
		median	7.8	17.3	0.040	38.4	0.010	0.36	4.18	84	0.026	0.114	0.77	785	11
4.0	12	average	7.3	16.7	0.570	91.0	0.037	1.19	6.36	129	0.088	0.191	1.13	1134	24
		median	7.5	16.9	0.183	65.4	0.020	0.17	6.75	101	0.031	0.086	0.69	896	21
4.2	14	average	9.4	18.0	0.150	63.2	0.032	0.77	4.93	123	0.045	0.130	0.64	930	16
		median	9.3	17.4	0.080	51.7	0.010	0.35	4.74	119	0.016	0.075	0.51	928	12
5.0	7	average	8.4	15.6	0.089	51.1	0.016	0.25	6.27	130	0.029	0.065	0.52	943	10
		median	7.4	16.0	0.070	47.5	0.010	0.07	4.76	107	0.001	0.029	0.49	922	12
5.2	10	average	5.2	15.6	1.478	145.8	0.052	0.35	7.61	125	0.704	1.068	3.52	1248	18
		median	4.5	15.8	0.070	50.4	0.001	0.12	6.21	40	0.063	0.125	0.85	851	14
6.0	8	average	10.0	16.3	0.054	50.3	0.023	0.44	5.41	151	0.015	0.056	0.54	914	11
		median	9.5	15.3	0.045	38.5	0.010	0.19	5.88	104	0.012	0.061	0.51	950	9
6.2	4	average	5.7	15.8	0.050	47.1	0.015	0.59	4.87	158	0.039	0.095	0.68	805	8
		median	6.4	15.8	0.040	45.3	0.010	0.49	4.71	103	0.022	0.077	0.69	824	7
7.0	2	average	4.3	14.7	1.390	385.5	0.165	1.42	9.70	44	0.160	0.433	2.04	6008	6
7.2	2	average	9.0	15.5	0.035	218.0	0.005	0.33	2.25	169	0.011	0.036	0.45	5494	15
8.0	7	average	8.0	17.0	0.033	49.8	0.003	0.42	5.39	912	0.017	0.054	0.31	1329	15
		median	9.0	17.9	0.040	43.2	0.000	0.37	6.46	94	0.007	0.045	0.27	873	11

Table 8. Average (mean) and median concentrations by site types grouped into major categories.

Site Type Category	Number of Samples		DO mg/L	Temperature degrees C.	NH3 mg/L	CL mg/L	NO2 mg/L	NO23 mg/L	SIO2 mg/L	SO4 mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	COND µmhos	SS mg/L
1.0 & 2.0 upstream, human	32	Average	7.6	17.6	0.125	82.9	0.02	0.71	5.42	151.6	0.040	0.110	0.70	1220	20
		Median	7.5	18.0	0.051	47.4	0.01	0.32	4.91	89.7	0.017	0.086	0.51	912	13
1.2 & 2.2 downstream, human	38	Average	6.7	17.0	1.449	126.1	0.10	1.82	6.58	179.8	0.285	0.421	1.87	1444	16
		Median	6.1	18.0	0.067	73.8	0.03	1.74	6.40	86.6	0.089	0.210	0.85	978	10
3.0,4.0, 5.0,6.0 Upstream , livestock	40	Average	8.5	16.9	0.236	116.4	0.03	1.09	5.61	144.8	0.095	0.174	0.82	1116	19
		Median	7.9	16.7	0.060	54.9	0.02	0.15	4.97	101.3	0.014	0.069	0.60	911	13
3.2, 4.2, 5.2, 6.2 downstream, livestock	46	Average	7.4	17.0	0.509	91.4	0.04	0.90	5.34	161.8	0.226	0.368	1.40	1009	15
		Median	7.3	16.7	0.050	50.5	0.01	0.23	4.39	91.0	0.026	0.102	0.65	851	12
8.0 Control watersheds	7	Average	9.4	17.0	0.033	49.8	0.00	0.42	5.39	912.3	0.017	0.054	0.31	1329	15
		Median	9.0	17.9	0.040	43.2	0.00	0.37	6.46	94.0	0.007	0.045	0.27	873	11

Table 9. Statistical significance of concentration differences between major site categories.

Site Type Category	Log NH3	Log NO23	Log TP	Log SRP	Log Chloride	Log Cond	DO	Log TKN
Human Upstream - Human Downstream	0.030	0.015	0.000	0.000	0.802	0.966	0.958	0.015
Livestock Downstream - Human Downstream	0.163	0.011	0.017	0.169	0.699	0.524	0.975	0.289
Livestock Downstream - Human Upstream	0.993	1.000	0.823	0.276	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.868
Livestock Upstream - Human Downstream	0.112	0.002	0.000	0.015	0.468	0.936	0.228	0.063
Livestock Upstream - Human Upstream	0.999	1.000	1.000	0.960	1.000	1.000	0.972	0.999
Livestock Upstream - Livestock Downstream	1.000	1.000	0.815	0.975	1.000	1.000	0.873	0.998
Reference Sites - Human Downstream	0.029	0.086	0.001	0.020	0.754	1.000	0.550	0.013
Reference Sites - Human Upstream	0.928	0.999	0.675	0.997	0.999	0.997	0.941	0.770
Reference Sites - Livestock Downstream	0.590	0.998	0.135	0.424	0.999	0.952	0.893	0.234
Reference Sites - Livestock Upstream	0.698	1.000	0.618	0.846	1.000	0.996	1.000	0.487

Figure 7. Boxplots of the log of the ammonia concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 8. Boxplots of the log of the nitrate concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 9. Boxplots of the log of the soluble reactive phosphorus concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 10. Boxplots of the log of the total phosphorus concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 11. Boxplots of the log of the chloride concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 12. Boxplots of the log of the conductivity concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 13. Boxplots of the log of the total Kjeldahl nitrogen concentrations for major site type categories.

Figure 14. Boxplots of the dissolved oxygen concentrations for major site type categories.

- 1 A detached value is defined as a value that is located more than 3.0 times the interquartile range beyond the box
- 2 An outside value is defined as one that lies between 1.5 and 3.0 interquartile ranges from the box
- 3 The upper whisker extends to the largest data point less than or equal to the upper quartile plus 1.5 times the interquartile range. Lower whisker is defined analogously.

The interquartile range is the difference between the 75th percentile value and the 25th percentile value. It is the height of the box.

Figure 15. Interpretation of boxplots, as presented in Figures 7-14.

Differences between average concentrations for the five station types were examined using analysis of variance (ANOVA). With the exception of dissolved oxygen, the concentrations were log-transformed before analysis in order to satisfy the ANOVA requirement for normally-distributed data. When an ANOVA produces a significant result, it indicates that one or more of the 10 possible pairs of station types have average concentrations which are significantly different from each other. These differences were evaluated using the Bonferroni post-hoc comparison test, the most conservative of the set of approaches usually used for this determination. The resulting probabilities for all pairwise comparisons are listed in Table 9. Significant differences (i.e. those with probabilities less than 0.05 (5%) that the difference is due to chance alone) are indicated with bold type.

Of the parameters examined, specific conductance, chloride, and dissolved oxygen did not produce a significant ANOVA result, and consequently no paired comparisons are statistically significant. All of the nutrient parameters had ANOVAs with a statistically significant station effect. It is apparent from the table that all of the significant differences for all parameters involve the human downstream stations. Examination of the average concentrations shown in Table 8 reveals that the concentrations at the human downstream stations are always higher than at the other type of station relative to which they show a significant difference.

Human downstream stations do not always have significantly higher average concentrations than other types of stations. The average nitrate concentration at human downstream stations is not significantly different than that at the reference stations. However, for the most easily interpreted comparisons - those between human downstream stations and either human upstream stations or reference stations - nine of the ten comparisons involving nutrient parameters show human downstream stations with a significantly higher average concentration than the comparison stations.

DISCUSSION

This study was designed to determine the extent to which livestock operations contributed to elevated nutrient concentrations in streams during low flow conditions. For comparison, impacts of human sources on nutrient concentrations were also examined. On average, sites immediately downstream from human sources had significantly higher nutrient concentrations than their upstream controls. On average, sites downstream from livestock sources were not significantly higher than their upstream controls. Furthermore, the average and median concentrations downstream from human sources were higher than the average and median concentrations downstream from livestock sources.

In terms of individual locations, some of the livestock impacted sites did have highly elevated nutrient concentrations. Further investigation of these sites would be warranted to determine more precisely the sources of the elevated nutrients. Also, some of the upstream control sites also had high nutrient concentrations, and should be investigated to determine sources.

Our laboratory loading studies conducted in these watersheds indicate that, in terms of watershed export, agricultural land uses are the dominant sources of nutrients. During the period from 1985 to 1994, only 5% of the total export of phosphorus from the Sandusky Watershed can be accounted for by municipal point sources. Even assuming comparable delivery of phosphorus from unsewered populations in the basin, human sources of phosphorus are dwarfed by agricultural sources. An even higher proportion of the nitrogen exported from the basin comes from agricultural sources.

Nutrient export from watersheds is largely associated with runoff events. Such events often have high nutrient concentrations combined with high flow. During such times, agricultural runoff clearly is impacting both ambient water quality in the stream and loading to downstream receiving waters. However, runoff events and high water periods occupy a small proportion of the time. As stream flows decrease, human sources of nutrients begin to exert their impacts on ambient water quality in the stream, even though their impacts on total loading to downstream receiving waters remains low.

A characteristic of human sources that makes them particularly important during low flow conditions is that human sources generally have continuous flow. Whether the human sources are failed septic systems/leach fields, aeration systems, package plants or municipal sewage treatment plants, the continuous water usage by humans results in a continuous waste stream finding its way to streams. In contrast, most livestock related sources find their way into streams only in connection with runoff conditions. Exceptions would be those livestock waste holding facilities that continuously leach. Also, spills, overflows of waste holding systems and flows connected with the transport and application of animal wastes can result in periodic delivery of nutrients into streams.

During the collection of samples for this survey, the effects of a spill from a waste holding pond in Wyandot County were observed (October 26, 1996). The resulting low dissolved oxygen in the stream resulted in a wildlife kill. Extra samples were collected in connection with this spill, but the sampling locations were not among those selected by local groups. The extra samples did indicate elevated nutrients, but the impacts of oxygen demanding wastes were more evident.

The results of this study suggest that, in terms of effects on ambient water quality in streams, as reflected in nutrient concentrations, human sources are more important than livestock sources. As noted above, agricultural sources dominate the loading of nutrients to receiving waters (e.g. Lake Erie) and agricultural sources dominate ambient water quality in streams during runoff periods. Determination of the role of livestock as a contributor to nutrient loading from the watershed and to ambient water quality during runoff events requires differing approaches than those used in this study. One approach would be to use automatic sampling upstream and downstream from potential livestock sources. The automatic samplers could be triggered during runoff-inducing rainfall events. A major difficulty in this approach, aside from its high costs, is that the stream responds to the total upstream watershed. The watershed response to the rainfall event may dwarf the effects of local runoff from the livestock site, making it impossible to sort out the local livestock impacts.

A second approach to assessing livestock's contribution to the watershed export and to high-flow ambient water quality is to use a nutrient budget approach. In such an approach, the contributions of livestock wastes to the overall nutrient inputs to the watershed are compared with other nutrient inputs, such as fertilizer, aerial deposition and nitrogen fixation. In the context of the overall nutrient budgets, the role of livestock can be estimated. A complication in this approach is uncertainty regarding the average delivery of nutrients from various sources to the stream systems. Given equal inputs of nutrients from livestock and fertilizer, would both have the same proportion of delivery to the stream system? Nutrient budget analyses are aided by information on the overall watershed export. Tributary loading studies, such as those conducted by the WQL for the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Division of Soil and Water Districts, provide overall watershed export data, so the relationships between nutrient inputs, nutrient export (loading) and high-flow ambient water quality can be assessed.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A small proportion of the sites deemed susceptible to livestock contamination has high nutrient levels, relative to upstream control sites, as anticipated. These sites bear further study to assess the need for remediation.
2. In general, sites downstream from potential livestock inputs did not have significantly higher nutrient concentrations than their upstream control sites.
3. Sites downstream from potential human inputs of nutrients, such as septic tanks, package plants and sewage treatment plants, did have significantly higher nutrient concentration than their upstream control sites.
4. On average, sites downstream from human inputs had significantly higher nitrate and phosphorus concentrations than sites downstream from potential livestock inputs.
5. Relative to ambient water quality in streams during low flow conditions, human inputs appear more important than livestock inputs as a source of elevated nutrient concentrations in the Sandusky River Watershed.
6. Assessment of livestock contributions to nutrient loading from the watershed and as a contributor to elevated nutrients during high flow conditions could be accomplished by analysis of watershed nutrient inputs coupled with detailed watershed loading studies. Such studies should be undertaken in agricultural watersheds having varying intensities of livestock production.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Relationship between Livestock Production and Water Resources in North Central Ohio

Appendix 2: Site locations and descriptions, and sample results for each county:

Crawford County
Hardin County
Marion County
Sandusky County
Seneca County
Wyandot County

Appendix 3: Scatterplots of replicate samples

Relationships Between Livestock Production and Water Resources in North Central Ohio

Impacts on stream nutrient levels during low and medium flows.

Guidelines for site selections for low flow synoptic survey (15 sites per county)

I. Review of Objectives of Low Flow Synoptic Stream Survey

Note: A synoptic survey is a survey in which many sites are collected in as short a time interval as possible. It is intended to provide a "snapshot" in time of water quality in the area. The more stations that are included in the snapshot, the better the spatial resolution of the survey. Under low flow conditions, stream quality usually does not change very rapidly. Consequently, the snapshot should characterize stream quality at those stations for an extended period of time, the duration of which depends on local hydrological conditions and pollutant inputs.

- A. The major objective of this project is to assess the nutrient levels and oxygen resources of small streams and rivers in the six county study area during base flow conditions, as they may be impacted by current livestock operations.
- B. A second objective of this project is to provide baseline nutrient data at selected sites, to support assessment of future livestock installations in the study area.
- C. A third objective of this project is to provide an indication of the impacts of municipal sewage and/or septic tank leachate on the nutrient levels and oxygen resources of the small streams and rivers of this area, for comparison with impacts of livestock operations.

Note: During base-flow/low-flow conditions, the majority of the water in a stream will be derived from springs and/or shallow ground water seepage. Shallow ground water seepage could be impacted by feedlots or fields receiving excessive manure applications. Lesser amounts of water may come from point sources of pollution, some of which could be associated with livestock operations. A second type of sampling program, the composite sampling program, can provide information regarding nutrient levels, as they are impacted by rainfall-runoff events. Such events may be more important as conveyors of livestock nutrients into stream systems than are inputs during base flow. A second set of guidelines will be developed for selecting sites for composite sampling programs.

II. General Guidelines for Site Selection

- A. Collections sites should be located at bridges over the streams. Where possible, the sampling team will use buckets to sample the stream from the bridge. If necessary, the sampling team will wade into the stream to collect the sample. This is often necessary in shallow streams during low flow to avoid getting bottom sediments mixed into the water sample. Try to avoid bridges where heavy traffic might make sampling dangerous.

If bridge locations are not possible, access to the stream across public or private property from a nearby road is acceptable, so long as permission from the landowner is arranged.

- B. Collection sites must have flowing water at the time of low flow sampling. If the stream is not flowing at the time of sample collection, erroneous results could be obtained. Pondered water in a stream may become highly concentrated through evaporation, yielding misleading results.
- C. The stream should be well mixed at the sampling site. If pollutants are entering along the edge of the stream just upstream from the sampling site, a sample collected at midstream could miss the upstream pollutant input. Normally, the sampling team will attempt to collect the sample at the position in the stream cross section where the greatest flow is occurring and where the stream is well-mixed.
- D. Select sites where comparative approaches can be used to aid in data interpretation.
1. Compare water samples collected upstream and downstream from a suspected pollutant source.
 2. When bracketing pollutant sources, collect the samples as close to the suspected point source input as possible, so long as the streams are well mixed. If the collections are made too far downstream from the inputs, uptake of nutrients by attached algae can mask the pollutant inputs. During low flows, waters moves very slowly through the stream system, allowing extended time periods for nutrient uptake by aquatic plants.
 3. Compare streams draining watersheds having different land-use or physical characteristics (i.e., comparing streams from forested, urbanized or agricultural watersheds.)
 4. In selecting sites for comparative watershed studies, try to have both watersheds in the same size range.
- E. Where possible, select sites to support efficient travel for sample collection. Avoid a large number of "outlier stations" that add many extra miles to the collection run. However, if outlier stations have features that uniquely support the study objectives, include them in the site selection.
- F. Clearly identify the collection site on a county road map or on the USGS quarter section map.
- G. Write down a brief rational for why each site was selected. Some of the sites may be serving as control stations for other sites. The upstream site for a pair of sites bracketing a suspected or known pollutant source would serve as a control for the site downstream from the possible pollutant source.

III. Specific Suggestions for Types of Sites for Livestock Impact Assessment.

- A. Stations upstream and downstream from a stream reach where concentrated livestock operations (feedlots or barn yards) are in close proximity to the stream or where livestock have direct access to the stream.
- B. Stations subtending watersheds with extensive application of animal wastes to cropland versus stations subtending watersheds with minimal application of animal wastes to cropland.
- C. For small streams, stations upstream and downstream from fields adjacent to the stream that receive heavy application of animal wastes.

- D. Stations subtending watersheds with high animal densities versus stations subtending watersheds with low animal densities. Neither watershed should contain significant point sources.
- E. Stations upstream and downstream from a point source of pollution (municipal waste treatment plant emptying into a small stream).
- F. Stations upstream or downstream from stream reaches likely to be receiving septic tank effluent or package plant effluent.
- G. Stations positioned to provide baseline data for assessment of future concentrated livestock operations.

IV. Recommendations for Site Types per County (15 sites per county)

- A. Each county should select two locations as described in III.A. above. This would require four sites.
- B. Each county should allocate four sites as described in III.B and III.C. above. This would require four sites.
- C. Each county should select a pair of sites bracketing a municipal sewage treatment plant emptying into a small stream (III. E. above). This would require two sites.
- D. Each county should select a pair of sites bracketing an area of concentrated septic tanks or package plant(s) (III.F. above). This would require two sites.
- E. The remaining three sites can be chosen at the discretion of local officials or residents.

(Note: the rationale underlying the selection of each sight should be briefly written down as noted above in II.G. and this rationale transferred to the WQL (Baker)).

V. Final Site Selection

- A. Local county SWCD and NRCS staff are requested to develop recommendations for the 15 sites in their county. They can involve any others they wish to for aid in location of sampling stations.
- B. WQL staff will meet with the above staff plus other concerned parties (local residents, health departments, farm groups, etc.) to agree on final station selections.
- C. Target Date for final site selection: September 15, 1996.
- D. Target Date for completion of synoptic survey, October 7, 1996.
- E. Parameters Tested:
 - In the Field -- dissolved oxygen and temperature
 - In the Lab -- total phosphorus, soluble reactive phosphorus, nitrate + nitrite, nitrite, ammonia, TKN, chloride, conductivity, sulfate, silica.

Appendix 2

Crawford County

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Table 1. Locations and site descriptions for Crawford County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Crawford # 1	5.0	Mile Run, Wyandot-Crawford Line Rd., sec. 11, Texas Twn.	Small watershed with minimal application of manure
Crawford # 2	6.2	Sycamore Creek, bridge on Miller Rd., section 17 Lykens Twn.	High animal densities, two dairy operations and a large hog operation
Crawford # 3	5.2	Tributary to Sycamore Creek, bridge on Orr Rd. sec 30, Lykens Twn.	One hog operations, two beef feedlots and a small dairy in watershed.
Crawford # 4	1.2	Sandusky River, bridge on Kerstetter Rd. (USGS gauge)	Downstream from Bucyrus sewage treatment plant
Crawford # 5	4.0	Little Scioto River, bridge on Caldwell Rd. sec 32, Bucyrus Twn.	Upstream from area receiving high manure, two 2,100 head finishing barns and 1,200 gestating sows
Crawford # 6	4.2	Little Scioto River, bridge on Monnett-New Winchester Rd. (SR 294), Sec 5 Dallas Twn.	Downstream from area receiving high manure, two 2,100 head finishing barns and 1,200 gestating sows
Crawford # 7	1.0	Sandusky River, bridge on Beechgrove Rd., sec 32, Liberty Twn.	Upstream from Bucyrus sewage treatment plant.
Crawford # 8	6.0	Broken Sword Creek, bridge on Schwemly Rd., sec 9, Liberty Twn.	Watershed with low animal density, one subwatershed has two dairy operations (see station 9)
Crawford # 9	5.2	Tributary to Broken Sword, Bridge on Ziegler Rd, sec 15, Liberty Twn.	Small watershed with two dairy operations, with heavy application of manure
Crawford #10	3.2	Sandusky River, bridge on Cox Road, section 26 Sandusky Twn.	Downstream from beef pastured on both sides of stream
Crawford #11	3.0	Sandusky River, bridge on Remlinger Road, Section 35, Sandusky Twn.	Upstream from reach pastured on both sides of stream. (County suggested Biddle Road bridge.)
Crawford #12	3.2	Olentangy River, bridge on Shearer Road, sec. 35 Whetstone Twn.	Downstream from dairy operation with storage facility next to stream and horse pastures along stream.
Crawford #13	3.0	Olentangy River, Bridge on Galion-New Winchester Rd.,	Upstream for dairy operation with storage facility and horse pastures.
Crawford #14	2.2	Tributary to Olentangy, Bridge on Biddle Road, sec 35, Polk Twn.	downstream from area of un-sewered subdivisions with failing septic systems near Galion.
Crawford #15	5.0	Mud Run (to Olentangy), bridge on Monnett-new Winchester Rd., Sec 1, Dallas Twn.	Small watershed with minimal application of manure

Figure 1. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Crawford County.

Table 2. Low flow synoptic survey results for Crawford County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	NO ₂ mg/L	NO ₃ mg/L	SiO ₂ MG/	SO ₄ mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Crawford #1	25				961017	858	7.43	13.7	0.04	71.8	0.00	-0.02	8.68	121.0	-0.003	0.021	0.173	12	1022
Crawford #1	25				970918	917	4.80	16.0	0.07	60.5	0.01	0.18	6.74	110.1	0.000	0.019	0.344	7	887
Crawford #1R					970918	917	4.80	16.0	0.07	58.7	0.01	0.20	11.72	96.0	-0.001	0.019	0.324	7	892
Crawford #2	6				961017	1156	3.22	14.9	0.01	50.5	-0.01	-0.03	1.51	115.9	0.014	0.073	0.638	1	876
Crawford #2	6		40 57 72 N	83 03 32 W	970918	936	6.80	16.7	0.11	40.0	0.00	0.23	3.02	84.8	0.018	0.063	0.734	8	650
Crawford #3	5				961017	1150	5.73	14.7	0.02	48.5	0.02	0.02	5.96	39.2	0.053	0.112	0.747	2	668
Crawford #3	5		40 56 05 N	83 03 69 W	970918	944	3.20	15.5	0.11	34.1	0.00	0.13	4.18	5.7	0.029	0.130	1.089	34	454
Crawford #4	1	Kerstetter			961017	1127	5.14	16.0	0.11	77.3	0.17	5.71	4.01	80.8	0.061	0.113	0.397	9	911
Crawford #4	1	Kerstetter	40 48 21 N	83 00 38 W	970918	1006	5.60	18.0	0.16	70.0	0.03	4.54	5.03	86.7	0.413	0.512	0.906	16	725
Crawford #5	24	L. Scioto			961017	938	5.29	13.0	0.05	67.4	0.01	0.04	1.59	346.7	0.013	0.053	0.308	2	1054
Crawford #5	24	L. Scioto	40 44 81 N	83 01 98 W	970918	1235	6.00	17.0	0.09	63.3	0.00	0.08	3.34	93.7	0.045	0.088	0.682	3	853
Crawford #6	4	L. Scioto			961017	929	2.80	14.2	0.03	69.2	0.01	-0.03	2.83	157.3	0.009	0.078	0.371	4	1018
Crawford #6R					961017	929	2.80	14.2	0.01	69.1	0.01	-0.03	2.79	266.7	0.012	0.077	0.323	5	1018
Crawford #6	4	L. Scioto	40 43 07 N	80 03 11 W	970918	1244	4.70	20.0	0.08	34.6	0.00	0.06	5.08	73.1	0.039	0.093	0.664	10	614
Crawford #7	21	Upstream Bucyrus			961017	1113	5.82	14.3	0.02	53.2	0.01	0.04	6.48	71.8	0.025	0.086	0.34	8	895
Crawford #7	21	Upstr. Bucy.	40 49 56 N	82 56 40 W	970918	1038	6.00	17.0	0.27	34.0	0.02	0.63	4.85	49.5	0.043	0.128	0.873	23	556
Crawford #8	26				961017	1100	9.42	15.8	0.04	26.3	0.01	-0.03	3.87	102.9	0.019	0.066	0.272	5	858
Crawford #8	26		40 53 44 N	82 55 29 W	970918	1050	11.20	19.0	0.05	25.0	0.00	0.04	6.68	106.4	0.014	0.040	0.399	10	785
Crawford #9	5				961017	1053	1.32	13.6	1.71	108.0	0.05	0.10	16.15	6.2	2.120	4.341	2.99	30	1318
Crawford #9	5		40 52 25 N	82 53 13 W	970918	1059	3.20	16.0	5.30	437.3	0.45	2.18	12.05	41.5	1.560	1.764	6.429	12	2020
Crawford #10	3				961017	1041	7.95	14.6	0.04	67.4	0.01	0.00	2.03	74.7	0.062	0.165	0.59	33	924
Crawford #10R					961017	1041	7.95	14.6	0.03	68.5	0.01	-0.02	2.08	80.0	0.060	0.163	0.498	30	924
Crawford #10	3		40 50 17 N	82 49 64 W	970918	1113	9.00	18.0	0.18	57.6	0.01	0.96	4.62	69.2	0.026	0.171	0.822	22	708
Crawford #11	23	51			961017	1032	6.98	14.1	0.03	69.7	0.02	0.01	2.38	71.8	0.068	0.140	0.458	9	947
Crawford #11	23	17940	49 71 N	82 49 34 W	970918	1120	7.50	17.0	0.12	58.1	0.01	1.33	4.84	71.1	0.100	0.164	0.812	10	731
Crawford #11R			40 49 71 N	82 49 34 W	970918	1120	7.50	17.0	0.16	59.7	0.01	1.37	4.96	77.1	0.110	0.162	0.798	10	731
Crawford #12	23	Olentangy R			961017	1003	5.55	14.2	0.02	70.8	0.06	5.24	2.86	588.9	0.514	0.702	0.628	9	899
Crawford #12	23	Olentangy	40 44 86 N	82 52 29 W	970918	1150	7.00	17.5	0.10	68.2	0.02	5.70	4.42	75.8	0.687	0.774	0.797	11	778
Crawford #13	3				961017	1010	7.42	14.7	0.01	72.3	0.06	7.08	3.75	93.1	0.811	0.964	0.609	6	900
Crawford #13	3		40 44 05 N	82 51 32 W	970918	1143	7.70	16.5	0.10	69.6	0.02	7.79	4.99	88.7	1.031	1.108	0.9	12	787
Crawford #14	2	Gallion/Olen			961017	1017	4.62	14.1	3.88	203.5	0.29	2.23	9.15	41.0	0.768	1.011	3.389	5	1451
Crawford #14	2	Gallion/Ol.	40 44 16 N	82 49 21 W	970918	1137	5.00	16.5	4.83	239.0	0.38	2.16	8.98	54.4	1.136	1.365	6.037	4	1462
Crawford #15	25				961017	952	8.98	12.6	0.05	35.1	0.02	0.01	4.62	351.0	0.001	0.039	0.492	14	1186
Crawford #15	25		40 43 08 N	82 57 79 W	970918	1204	10.80	17.5	0.07	33.8	0.00	0.05	4.76	107.4	0.013	0.027	0.563	4	1028

Table 3. Locations and site descriptions for Hardin County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Hardin # 1	1.0	Blanchard River, bridge on CR 20, west of CR 183	Upstream from Forest point source
Hardin # 2	1.2	Blanchard River, bridge on CR 10, east of CR 183	Downstream from Forest point source
Hardin # 3	5.2	Little Tymochtee Creek, bride on CR 205, section 31 Jackson Twn.	Watershed with extensive application of animal wastes.
Hardin # 4	4.2	Little Tymochtee Creek, bridge on TR 74, section 6, Goshen Twn.	Downstream from fields receiving heavy application of animal waste.
Hardin # 5	4.0	Little Tymochtee Creek, bridge on CR 90, section 7, Goshen Twn.	Upstream from fields receiving heavy application of animal waste.
Hardin # 6	5.0	Reelhorn Run, bridge on TR 90, west of CR 215	Watershed with minimal application of animal wastes
Hardin # 7	2.2	Reelhorn Run, bridge on TR 100, section 18, Goshen Twn.	Downstream from area receiving septic tank effluent
Hardin # 8	5.0	Ränge Run, bridge on CR 100, south of SR 67	Watershed with minimal application of animal wastes
Hardin # 9	2.0	Reelhorn Run, bridge on CR 120, section 30, Goshen Twn.	Upstream from area receiving septic tank effluents.
Hardin # 10	5.2 (6.2)	North (main branch Pawpaw Run, bridge on TR 245, section 35, Goshen Twn.	Watershed with extensive application of animal wastes and high animal density
Hardin # 11	6.0	south br. Pawpaw Run, bridge on TR 245, section 35, Goshen Twn.	Watershed with low animal density
Hardin # 12	1.2	Scioto River, bridge on CR 175	Downstream from Kenton sewage treatment plant
Hardin # 13	1.0	Scioto River, bridge on CR 130	Upstream from Kenton sewage treatment plant

Figure 2. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Hardin County

Table 4. Low flow synoptic survey results for Hardin County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	NO ₂ mg/L	NO ₃ mg/L	SiO ₂ MG/	SO ₄ mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Hardin #1		Blanchard	40 48 21 N	83 33 47 W	970905	1425	8.00	18.5	0.05	38.4	0.00	0.17	2.18	57.6	0.016	0.070	0.429	13	802
Hardin #1R			40 48 21 N	83 33 47 W	970905	1425	8.00	18.5	0.02	38.4	0.00	0.16	2.45	121.7	0.004	0.072	0.497	15	804
Hardin #1		Blanchard			971010	1316	4.00	18.2	0.05	58.7	0.00	-0.05	2.10	259.9	0.086	0.142	0.531	5	1048
Hardin #1R					971010	1317	4.00	18.2	0.07	59.7	0.00	-0.02	2.00	262.9	0.079	0.141	0.489	5	1049
Hardin #2		Blanchard	40 49 10 N	83 32 96 W	970905	1435	9.40	18.2	0.00	36.4	0.00	0.19	2.37	148.9	0.014	0.088	0.373	8	779
Hardin #2		Blanchard			971010	1326	3.30	18.0	0.06	56.8	0.00	-0.07	2.57	238.5	0.082	0.216	0.594	6	1034
Hardin #3	5		40 43 83 N	83 30 96 W	970905	1140	7.30	15.3	0.03	42.0	0.00	0.18	2.88	33.5	0.008	0.051	0.398	7	811
Hardin #3	5		40 43 86 N	83 30 94 W	971010	1102	2.00	16.5	0.03	36.2	0.00	-0.08	9.32	159.3	0.072	0.300	0.334	12	890
Hardin #4	4		40 43 41 N	83 31 73 W	970905	1149	12.70	17.7	0.01	40.9	0.00	0.02	3.29	44.1	0.004	0.030	0.361	6	810
Hardin #4	4		40 43 46 N	83 31 73 W	971010	1108	9.40	16.0	0.10	35.5	0.00	-0.06	9.61	155.1	0.007	0.063	0.514	4	868
Hardin #5	24				970905	1155	9.10	16.3	0.01	67.4	0.02	0.65	4.94	107.9	-0.001	0.077	0.498	18	938
Hardin #5	24		40 42 15 N	83 32 19 W	971010	1114	5.60	16.1	0.25	77.7	0.00	-0.06	8.17	135.0	0.103	0.206	0.960	21	976
Hardin #6 - no water	25				971010														
Hardin #7	2		40 41 47 N	83 31 41 W	970905	1200	7.00	14.6	0.24	97.7	0.11	1.30	7.18	70.8	0.040	0.126	0.874	18	959
Hardin #7	2		40 41 25 N	83 31 40 W	971010	1121	4.50	15.0	24.64	43.0	0.78	2.70	14.84	223.0	2.600	2.406	16.228	18	1301
Hardin #8	25		40 41 17 N	83 29 73 W	970905	1212	6.00	15.3	0.15	79.9	0.03	0.55	4.68	99.6	0.109	0.188	0.726	15	922
Hardin #8 - no water	25				971010														
Hardin #9	22		40 39 36 N	83 30 62 W	970905	1240	2.90	14.7	0.09	155.6	0.02	0.32	11.79	32.0	0.166	0.359	1.570	2	1194
Hardin #9 - no water	22				971010														
Hardin #10	6		40 39 17 N	83 26 37 W	970905	1225	11.00	16.7	0.05	58.8	0.00	0.63	6.46	49.4	0.072	0.120	0.453	9	924
Hardin #10	6		40 39 23 N	83 26 30 W	971010	1139	0.00	16.0	7.41	601.7	0.00	-0.07	14.51	816.1	3.120	3.721	21.248	31	4030
Hardin #11	5		40 39 06 N	83 26 36 W	970905	1230	4.60	14.8	0.07	30.0	0.01	0.31	3.74	70.3	0.008	0.058	0.587	6	788
Hardin #11R			40 39 06 N	83 26 36 W	970905	1230	4.60	14.8	0.08	30.6	0.01	0.31	3.80	82.8	0.008	0.058	0.705	4	786
Hardin #11 - no water	5				971010														
Hardin #12	1	Scioto, Kenton	40 38 25 N	83 34 46 W	970905	1300	9.30	18.2	0.06	37.8	0.01	2.02	4.17	132.3	0.286	0.398	0.731	16	951
Hardin #12	1	Scioto, Kenton			971010	1158	1.70	18.3	2.54	37.5	0.31	2.37	5.76	232.7	0.540	0.784	3.202	23	952
Hardin #12R					971010	1159	1.70	18.3	2.36	38.3	0.31	2.39	5.80	241.1	0.635	0.785	2.860	22	951
Hardin #13	21		40 38 36 N	83 33 34 W	970905	1315	10.00	17.3	0.03	26.8	0.00	0.29	4.49	166.0	0.007	0.048	0.489	15	913
Hardin #13	21		40 38 35 N	83 38 36 W	971010	1214	2.90	18.2	0.05	26.8	0.00	-0.06	5.57	215.8	0.007	0.077	0.464	13	966

Table 5. Locations and site descriptions for Marion County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Marion # 1	3.2	Little Tymochtee Cr., bridge on Wyan. CR 142A at county line	
Marion # 2	3.2	Trib to Tymochtee, Bridge on Fail Rd, north of Robins Rd	
Marion # 3	6.2	Tymochtee Cr., bridge on Decliff Rd.	
Marion # 4	6.0	Trib to Tymochtee, bridge on Irvin-Shoots Rd, east of Decliff	
Marion # 5	6.0	Trib to Tymochtee, Osbun Rd. north of Marseilles-Galion Rd.	
Marion # 6		Trib to Tymochtee bridge on Irvin-Shoots Rd, east of Osbun Rd.	
Marion # 7	2.2	Tymochtee Cr., bridge on SR 309, west of Meeker Rd.	
Marion # 8	2.0	Tymochtee Cr., bridge on Meeker Rd, south of Frame Rd.	
Marion # 9	2.2	Tymochtee Cr., bridge on Bumford Rd, south of 309	
Marion # 10		Little Sandusky R., Bridge on TR 68, Marion/Wyan County line	Fertilizer Plant impacts
Marion # 11	2.2	Little Sandusky R., Bridge on SR 231, west side of Morral	
Marion # 12	2.0	Little Sandusky R, bridge on Brown Rd, east side of Morral	

Figure 3. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Marion County.

Table 6. Low flow synoptic survey results for Marion County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O2, mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH3 mg/L	CL mg/L	NO2 mg/L	NO23 mg/L	SIO2 MG/	SO4 mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Marion #1	3				961026	1606	0.65	13.7	0.00	35.8	0.03	-0.02	5.50	67.1	0.338	0.796	1.668	11	787
Marion #1	3		40 41 23 N	83 24 72 W	970918	1514	8.60	19.5	0.03	37.6	0.00	0.02	1.88	68.4	0.012	0.053	0.553	13	711
Marion #1R			40 41 23 N	83 24 72 W	970918	1514	8.60	19.5	0.03	36.5	0.00	0.02	1.96	75.1	0.009	0.052	0.535	10	712
Marion #2	3				961026	1552	1.28	13.3	0.01	27.8	0.03	-0.02	9.09	104.7	0.052	0.156	0.871	4	785
Marion #2	3		40 40 48 N	83 23 42 W	970918	1506	7.30	20.8	0.04	38.4	0.00	0.03	2.14	78.2	0.022	0.106	0.935	20	704
Marion #3	6				961026	1537	6.72	12.9	0.01	59.8	0.05	0.74	8.55	341.5	0.025	0.081	0.544	5	924
Marion #3R					961026	1537	6.72	12.9	0.01	58.5	0.06	0.73	8.36	279.5	0.025	0.081	0.521	6	925
Marion #3	6		40 40 28 N	83 20 58 W	970918	1456	6.00	18.5	0.07	37.9	0.02	1.42	6.39	91.0	0.098	0.161	0.804	17	771
Marion #4	26				961026	1543	6.95	13.5	0.01	62.0	0.08	1.78	7.51	273.6	0.024	0.067	0.447	3	944
Marion #4	26		40 39 49 N	83 20 55 W	970918	1452	6.00	18.0	0.11	55.8	0.02	1.01	6.23	96.4	0.033	0.063	0.538	8	1031
Marion #5	26				961026	1529	16.50	13.1	0.01	33.4	0.04	0.34	5.52	385.9	0.008	0.030	0.488	14	955
Marion #5	26		40 40 51 N	83 19 43 W	970918	1444	15.80	25.0	0.12	43.5	0.01	0.06	3.24	104.4	0.009	0.059	0.695	31	993
Marion #6					961026	1519	6.42	13.2	0.01	56.8	0.07	1.41	9.14	85.2	0.029	0.087	0.481	3	870
Marion #6			40 38 48 N	83 18 68 W	970918	1437	8.20	18.5	0.12	42.2	0.01	1.46	5.46	67.5	0.100	0.157	0.763	2	717
Marion #7	2				961026	1511	5.33	13.4	0.05	92.3	0.07	1.00	9.30	99.3	0.059	0.114	0.564	7	1052
Marion #7	2		40 38 51 N	83 18 52 W	970918	1426	3.50	18.0	2.12	195.9	0.10	1.61	8.34	84.3	0.369	0.517	3.027	11	1112
Marion #8	22	also 26			961026	1503	5.17	13.2	0.01	94.0	0.09	1.14	8.78	264.0	0.036	0.099	0.415	3	1039
Marion #8	22	also26	40 38 16 N	83 18 31 W	970918	1423	3.30	18.2	0.16	102.1	0.04	0.93	6.25	80.0	0.137	0.199	0.889	8	966
Marion #9	2				961026	1452	17.00	14.9	0.01	167.5	0.10	2.02	7.51	279.8	0.117	0.255	0.418	6	1387
Marion #9	2		40 37 32 N	83 14 95 W	970918	1415	7.20	18.0	0.11	331.4	0.03	5.54	12.41	99.2	0.210	0.445	0.811	18	1631
Marion #10		Fertilizer Plant?			961026	1435	5.31	13.5	0.93	78.1	0.32	5.02	11.86	337.5	1.700	3.319	1.562	8	1093
Marion #10R		Fertilizer Plant?			961026	1435	5.31	13.5	0.99	76.1	0.32	4.84	12.08	258.3	2.222	3.320	1.510	6	1095
Marion #10		Fertilizer Plant?	40 42 12 N	83 14 81 W	970918	1530	5.00	19.1	0.05	45.4	0.03	1.45	9.24	84.2	0.097	0.188	0.670	15	791
Marion #11	2				961026	1426	5.80	12.8	0.00	75.3	0.09	1.99	8.03	98.3	0.113	0.217	0.639	10	1004
Marion #11	2		40 41 29 N	83 13 43 W	970918	1536	5.60	18.4	0.09	72.2	0.04	0.52	9.80	86.5	0.092	0.143	0.555	7	963
Marion #11R	2		40 41 29 N	83 13 43 W	970918	1536	5.60	18.4	0.10	71.9	0.04	0.52	9.75	89.3	0.098	0.144	0.529	9	971
Marion #12	22				961026	1413	11.02	13.0	0.01	41.6	0.03	0.40	11.54	118.3	0.005	0.037	0.152	14	1040
Marion #12	22		40 41 65 N	83 11 60 W	970918	1546	9.40	21.0	0.28	38.0	0.02	0.78	12.16	92.9	0.027	0.037	0.316	18	905
Rt67 Ltl Tymocht					961026	1623	5.99	13.7	0.01	54.2	0.04	-0.01	3.52	72.3	0.051	0.113	0.750	2	792
Tymocht@Marsll					961026	1632	6.43	12.7	0.00	54.5	0.07	0.43	8.55	345.6	0.032	0.087	0.578	5	1025

Table 7. Locations and site descriptions for Sandusky County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Sandusky #1	4.2	Indian Creek, bridge on CR 181	Sites 1 & 2 bracket an area that receives extensive applications of animal waste. Site 1 is in the middle of application area and site 2 is downstream.
Sandusky #2	4.2	Indian Creek, bridge on CR 193	See site 2 in Seneca County for upstream control
Sandusky # 3	2.0	F. H. Bartson Ditch, bridge on Cole Rd.	Sites 3 &4 bracket an area of septic systems and a golf course, site 3 is upstream. Both sites are downstream from a dairy farm.
Sandusky #4	2.2	F. H. Bartson Ditch, bridge on CR 198	Site 4 is downstream of septic tank area and golf course,
Sandusky #5	8.0	Green Creek, bridge on Cole Rd.	potential site for future development
Sandusky #6	7.0	Pickerel Creek, bridge on CR 268	Sites 6 & 7 bracket an area that has received extensive application of sewage sludge for several years. Site 6 is upstream.
Sandusky #7	7.2	Pickerel Creek, bridge on SR 101	Site 7 is downstream from area receiving heavy application of sewage sludge
Sandusky #8	2.0	Muskellunge Cr., bridge on CR 41	Sites 8-10 bracket an area receiving effluent from a housing development package plant, extensive application of animal waste from two livestock operations, and a golf course. Site 8 is the upstream site.
Sandusky #9	2.2	Muskellunge Cr., bridge on CR 108, east side	Site 9 is immediately downstream from the package plant.
Sandusky #10	5.2 (2.2)	Muskellunge Cr., bridge on Napoleon Rd. (CR 51)	Site 10 is further downstream, below the area of livestock influence and the golf course.
Sandusky #11	1.0	Muddy Creek, bridge on SR 590	This pair of sites brackets a municipal sewage treatment plant in Lindsey. Site 11 is upstream.
Sandusky #12	1.2	Muddy Creek, bridge on CR 106	Site 12 is downstream.
Sandusky #13	6.0	Nine Mile Creek, bridge on CR 92	Little or no animal waste is applied and no sizable livestock operations are located in the Nine Mile Creek watershed upstream from this location
Sandusky #14	4.0	Sugar Creek, bridge on CR 33	Sites 14 & 15 bracket an area where a concentrated livestock operation (large duck farm) is close to the stream. The area also receives extensive applications of animal waste. Site 14 is upstream.
Sandusky #15	4.2	Sugar Creek, bridge on CR 10	Site 15 is downstream Site 14.

Figure 4. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Sandusky County.

Table 8. Low flow synoptic survey results for Sandusky County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	NO ₂ mg/L	NO ₂₃ mg/L	SiO ₂ MG/	SO ₄ mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Sandusky #1	5	Middle			961015	1532	15.24	16.9	0.08	46.7	0.01	1.36	6.60	115.1		0.028	0.307	18.2	1012
Sandusky #1	5	Middle	41 16 25 N	83 07 74 W	970916	1400	13.00	26.0	0.11	50.6	0.01	1.53	5.27	122.2		0.019	0.281	14	922
Sandusky #2	5	downstream			961015	1541	15.45	16.1	0.05	52.7	0.03	0.78	6.90	252.6	0.000	0.031	0.321	10	1050
Sandusky #2	5	downstream	41 16 87 N	83 08 90 W	970916	1406	15.20	25.5	0.10	55.5	0.02	1.03	5.22	144.0	0.006	0.022	0.271	16	933
Sandusky #3	22	also type 5?			961015	1133	8.95	11.7	0.20	524.2	0.08	1.07	4.00	306.4	0.008	0.080	0.524	65	10050
Sandusky #3	22	also type 5?	41 19 26 N	83 04 90 W	970916	1225	7.50	21.0	1.56	305.9	0.24	5.46	8.97	100.0	0.255	0.142	2.518	130	1672
Sandusky #4	2				961015	1115	5.50	12.1	1.02	698.7	0.27	2.05	6.43	722.1	0.206	0.314	1.492	14	13510
Sandusky #4	2		41 20 74 N	83 04 08 W	970916	1217	5.90	20.0	1.36	840.0	0.25	0.89	2.31	415.4	0.159	0.364	2.080	14	3540
Sandusky #5	28	baseline, development			961015	1127	9.13	12.1	0.01	27.3	0.00	0.10	9.27	4900.0	0.007	0.030	-0.171	11	2920
Sandusky #5	28	baseline	41 19 27 N	83 03 59 W	970916	1236	8.90	16.0	0.05	25.0	0.02	0.37	7.24	1150.2	0.002	0.047	0.243	20	2310
Sandusky #6	27				961015	1159	3.42	11.4	1.46	586.3	0.16	0.79	10.57	96.9	0.313	0.572	1.971	9	10700
Sandusky #6	27		41 18 15 N	82 56 17 W	970916	1258	5.20	18.0	1.32	184.7	0.17	2.05	8.83	-9.0	0.007	0.293	2.099	3	1316
Sandusky #7	7				961015	1151	7.44	11.5	0.02	310.2	0.01	0.05	4.31	239.0	0.003	0.042	0.465	24	9920
Sandusky #7	7		41 19 36 N	82 56 50 W	970916	1252	10.50	19.5	0.05	125.8	0.00	0.61	0.19	98.7	0.018	0.029	0.429	6	1068
Sandusky #8	22				961015	946	3.10	11.3	0.00	39.1	0.00	0.05	2.14	72.7	0.003	0.094	0.493	43	686
Sandusky #8	22		41 19 58 N	83 13 16 W	970916	1100	7.10	18.0	0.05	30.1	0.00	0.32	2.94	47.8	0.005	0.083	0.371	9	644
Sandusky #9	2				961015	937	2.97	11.8	-0.01	168.2	0.09	5.26	6.22	77.9	0.910	1.304	0.789	6	1317
Sandusky #9R					961015	937	2.97	11.8	-0.01	160.9	0.10	5.19	6.08	73.6	1.110	1.364	0.756	4	1318
Sandusky #9	2		41 20 06 N	83 12 24 W	970916	1106	6.90	18.0	0.07	45.5	0.00	0.88	3.35	55.9	0.086	0.138	0.373	10	711
Sandusky #10	5	also 2			961015	925	7.80	12.0	0.03	52.2	-0.01	0.04	1.40	61.3	0.001	0.048	0.599	16	716
Sandusky #10	5	also 2	41 20 99 N	83 10 82 W	970916	1114	10.00	20.0	0.09	38.9	0.01	0.38	3.19	37.3	0.008	0.093	0.954	30	653
Sandusky #11	21				961015	1047	7.81	13.2	0.01	143.9	0.01	0.46	1.48	320.1	0.008	0.038	0.397	10	1580
Sandusky #11	21		41 24 87 N	83 13 25 W	970916	1121	9.00	20.0	0.06	106.7	0.00	0.18	2.01	427.1	0.004	0.051	0.389	18	1191
Sandusky #11R			41 24 87 N	83 13 25 W	970916	1121	9.00	20.0	0.07	106.0	0.00	0.17	1.92	367.0	0.003	0.051	0.536	19	1186
Sandusky #12	1				961015	1059	5.21	11.9	0.00	93.0	0.02	1.68	3.17	73.2	0.127	0.206	0.527	5	1061
Sandusky #12	1		41 25 36 N	83 12 10 W	970916	1143	7.30	19.5	0.04	107.1	0.00	0.46	1.80	316.8	0.005	0.054	0.268	6	1182
Sandusky #13	26				961015	1039	9.53	11.0	0.02	126.4	0.01	0.03	6.48	69.3	0.002	0.064	0.881	9	956
NO WATER 1997	26																		
Sandusky #14	25				961015	1012	6.60	10.1	1.14	174.6	0.02	0.09	9.25	189.3	0.111	0.395	1.858	27	1725
Sandusky #14	25		41 17 87 N	83 24 70 W	970916	1038	10.50	19.0	0.32	76.4	0.04	0.14	5.36	28.9	0.012	0.083	0.544	16	767
Sandusky #15	5				961015	1004	5.77	10.5	1.20	155.0	0.21	0.63	6.01	140.7	0.163	0.375	2.387	36	1413
Sandusky #15	5		41 18 18 N	83 24 00 W	970916	1044	9.10	18.5	0.08	75.4	0.01	0.01	3.68	20.8	0.023	0.102	0.515	21	776

Table 9. Locations and site descriptions for Seneca County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Seneca #1	5.0	Muskellunge Cr., bridge on CR 62 at county line	Control site for Sandusky County Site #8
Seneca #2	4.0	Indian Creek, bridge on TR 75 (Jopp Rd)	Control site for Sandusky County Site #1
Seneca #3	8.0	Wolf Creek, bridge on E. Township Line Rd.(T101 s of SR 12)	Baseline site, prevalence of lake plain influence
Seneca #4	1.2	Wolf Creek, off (s) of SR 18, e of T205	Downstream from Hammer-Heinsman Subdivision treatment plant
Seneca #5	1.0	Wolf Creek, bridge on Center Rd (T112) e of SR 587	Upstream from Hammer-Heinsman Subdivision
Seneca #6	3.2 (2.2)	East Br. Wolf Cr., bridge on CR 592	Downstream from animal concentrations and Seneca #7
Seneca #7	2.2	East Br. Wolf Cr., bridge on CR 38	Downstream from possible septic tank problems
Seneca #8	2.0	East Br. Wolf Cr., bridge on CR 11	Upstream from sites #7 & #8
Seneca #9	8.0	Beaver Creek, bridge on SR 101	Baseline site, till plain with low erosion rates.
Seneca #10	8.0	Rock Creek at Rebecca St Bridge, Tiffin	Baseline site, till plain with high erosion rates.
Seneca #11	2.2	Honey Creek, bridge on CR 19	Downstream from Honey Creek subdivision
Seneca #12	2.0	Honey Creek, bridge on CR 16	Upstream from Site #11
Seneca #13	3.2	Rock Creek, bridge on CR 16, east of Gillig Rd	Downstream from animal concentrations
Seneca #14	3.0	Rock Creek, bridge on CR 16 west of Stever Rd	Upstream from animal concentrations (site #13)
Seneca #15	3.2	trib to Rock Cr, bridge on CR 16, east of Stever Rd and Rock Creek	Downstream from dairy operation
Seneca #16	3.0	trib to Rock Cr., bridge on SR 67 south of US 224	Upstream from dairy operation
Seneca #17	2.2	Honey Cr., bridge on SR 100/SR 67	Downstream from Melmore

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Seneca #18	3.2 (2.0)	Honey Cr., adjacent to TR 163A	Downstream from animal concentrations , upstream from Melmore
Seneca #19	3.0	Honey Creek, bridge on CR 6, east of SR 100	Upstream of #17 & #18
Seneca #20	2.2	Honey Creek, bridge on Cemetery Rd. (TR 173)	Downstream of Bloomville
Seneca #21	2.0	Honey Creek, bridge on Tiffin- Caroline Rd (TR 88)	Upstream from Bloomville
Seneca #22a	1.2	Honey Creek, bridge on Slessman Rd (TR 79)	Downstream from Attica
Seneca #23	1.0	Honey Creek, bridge on Caroline Rd. East (TR 88) east of TR 191	Upstream of Attica

Figure 5. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Seneca County.

Table 10. Low flow synoptic survey results for Seneca County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O2, mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH3 mg/L	CL mg/L	NO2 mg/L	NO23 mg/L	SIO2 MG/	SO4 mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Seneca #1	22	Sandusky #8			961015	1610	17.54	16.0	0.01	47.5	0.01	0.07	2.66	61.4	-0.003	0.029	0.335	12	774
Seneca #1	22	Sand. #8	41 15 29 N	83 20 52 W	970916	1022	3.50	18.0	0.23	29.0	0.04	0.89	11.72	61.9	0.089	0.134	1.011	8	779
Seneca #1R			41 15 29 N	83 20 52 W	970916	1022	3.50	18.0	0.21	28.9	0.04	0.91	11.93	58.4	0.058	0.129	0.728	8	779
Seneca #2	25	Sandus #1&2			961015	1522	2.60	16.3	3.26	406.8	0.08	0.20	8.13	187.1	0.260	0.211	3.064	78	3080
Seneca #2	25	Sand 1&2	41 15 00 N	83 06 72 W	970916	1417	7.50	21.4	0.09	41.2	0.00	0.09	8.16	76.9	0.011	0.070	0.543	40	774
Seneca #3	28	lake plain soils			961015	1627	13.04	17.9	0.01	70.8	0.00	0.02	1.51	63.7	0.000	0.045	0.407	22	727
Seneca #3	28	lake plain	41 12 28 N	83 18 24 W	970916	1008	7.20	20.0	0.04	105.4	0.00	0.14	0.58	2.7	0.037	0.058	0.610	30	995
Seneca #4	2		41 08 14 N	83 23 06 W	970916	948	2.70	20.0	0.66	118.5	0.11	1.80	4.73	75.3	0.214	0.459	2.023	72	992
Seneca #5	22		41 07 42 N	83 22 16 W	970916	933	6.20	18.0	0.05	65.1	0.01	0.56	4.96	45.6	0.095	0.193	0.991	13	667
Seneca #6	4				961015	1641	12.36	17.1	0.01	78.7	0.01	0.35	4.18	83.7	0.008	0.072	0.468	6	949
Seneca #6	4		41 10 90 N	83 11 76 W	970916	1717	9.50	21.0	0.03	68.6	0.01	1.25	5.27	112.8	0.063	0.154	0.684	19	851
Seneca #7	2	Wolf Creek E			961015	1649	5.00	15.1	0.00	65.1	0.00	0.32	5.60	75.7	0.027	0.088	0.445	5	857
Seneca #7	2	Wolf E	41 10 08 N	83 11 97 W	970916	1724	8.80	19.2	0.05	80.1	0.00	0.93	5.90	118.5	0.077	0.144	0.448	12	930
Seneca #8	22	also 24, Wolfe E			961015	1657	7.77	15.9	0.01	71.9	0.01	0.29	4.36	84.2	0.019	0.084	0.426	9	907
Seneca #8R					961015	1657	7.77	15.9	0.01	71.7	0.00	0.30	4.27	84.2	0.022	0.085	0.238	9	915
Seneca #8	22	also 24, Wolf E	41 09 57 N	83 12 33 W	970916	1729	12.60	22.0	0.05	82.9	0.00	0.88	5.49	122.1	0.066	0.129	0.487	7	947
Seneca #9	28	base, low erosion			961015	1505		14.3	0.01	47.6	0.00	0.39	6.46	94.0	0.003	0.035	0.273	6	836
Seneca #9R					961015	1505		14.3	0.00	45.9	0.01	0.39	6.33	90.5	0.003	0.037	0.265	6	837
Seneca #9	28	base, low erosion	41 13 72 N	83 01 28 W	970916	1430	8.10	19.0	0.06	43.2	0.00	1.19	5.76	52.8	0.065	0.125	0.540	8	641
Seneca #10	28	base, high erosion			970916	1800	9.80	19.5	0.05	29.2	0.00	0.70	6.94	122.9	0.008	0.036	0.259	9	873
Seneca #11	2	Honey C subdiv			961016	1410	6.22	17.4	0.01	35.7	0.01	0.22	4.99	141.2	0.014	0.139	0.533	51	928
Seneca #11	2	Honey C subdiv	41 04 97 N	83 11 38 W	970916	1654	7.30	20.0	0.05	17.3	0.00	2.61	7.64	61.8	0.027	0.129	0.885	32	536
Seneca #11R			41 04 97 N	83 11 38 W	970916	1654	7.30	20.0	0.03	17.5	0.00	2.60	7.47	56.1	0.018	0.128	1.010	33	537
Seneca #12	22	upstream 11			961016	1422	12.57	17.4	0.03	35.9	0.00	0.35	3.58	129.7	0.003	0.053	0.351	10	911
Seneca #12	22	upstream 11	41 03 92 N	83 10 66 W	970916	1646	9.30	22.5	0.09	17.2	0.00	2.73	7.00	73.3	0.025	0.117	0.779	26	537

Table 10, continued. Low flow synoptic survey results for Seneca County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	NO ₂ mg/L	NO ₃ mg/L	SIO ₂ MG/	SO ₄ mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos
Seneca #13	4	Rock C			961016	1436	13.67	19.2	0.02	15.3	0.03	2.64	3.32	1617.7	-0.002	0.024	0.297	1.7	854
Seneca #13	4	Rock C	41 03 96 N	83 06 73 W	970916	1638	13.00	25.0	0.11	26.6	0.02	1.76	4.29	114.7	0.002	0.048	0.439	4	757
Seneca #14	24	Rock C, some 4			961016	1443	9.85	17.2	-0.01	14.8	0.00	-0.02	6.95	604.0	0.000	0.133	1.057	22	994
Seneca #14	24	Rock cr.some 4	41 03 95 N	83 05 81 W	970916	1632	12.00	22.0	0.05	27.0	0.00	-0.02	4.01	105.1	0.003	0.052	0.564	18	730
Seneca #15	4	Rock C			961016	1131	5.40	13.7	5.71	840.3	0.37	0.92	13.23	486.8	0.412	0.661	5.330	40	4450
Seneca #15	4	Rock C	41 03 89 N	83 04 97 W	970916	1629	6.10	18.0	0.07	120.4	0.01	0.36	2.76	105.9	0.011	0.094	0.765	7	992
Seneca #16	24	Rock C			961016	1613	11.45	19.0	0.02	110.0	0.01	0.06	1.19	82.7	-0.002	0.058	0.858	23	1046
Seneca #16	24	Rock C	41 04 66 N	83 03 48 W	970916	1623	8.00	20.0	0.03	53.9	0.00	0.09	3.54	1.6	0.014	0.081	0.663	12	553
Seneca #17	2	2			961016	1110	7.00	14.7	0.24	33.8	0.03	3.41	3.17	47.5	0.031	0.091	1.605	6	768
Seneca #17R	2	2			961016	1110	7.00	14.7	0.24	35.0	0.05	3.41	3.20	55.7	0.031	0.091	0.753	6	770
Seneca #17	2	2	41 01 37 N	83 06 60 W	970916	1606	9.60	21.0	0.06	15.4	0.00	3.33	8.03	47.5	0.038	0.127	0.890	23	487
Seneca #17A	2	2	41 01 19 N	83 07 89 W	970916	1613	9.40	21.0	0.05	16.1	0.00	3.28	7.63	44.7	0.043	0.129	0.975	21	493
Seneca #18	4	also 22			961016	1058	7.60	13.5	0.00	21.3	0.04	3.31	3.26	35.7	0.004	0.033	0.385	6	688
Seneca #18	4	also 22	41 01 15 N	83 06 40 W	970916	1602	9.30	20.5	0.04	15.7	0.00	3.30	7.82	35.2	0.035	0.130	1.108	24	487
Seneca #19	24	also 22			961016	1114	6.75	14.3	0.01	25.0	0.03	1.16	1.94	44.7	0.002	0.045	0.533	6	664
Seneca #19	24	also 22	41 01 37 N	83 05 79 W	970916	1555	9.50	21.0	0.04	16.0	0.00	2.99	7.80	51.5	0.037	0.133	0.925	24	478
Seneca #20	1	Bloomville			961016	1459	15.49	20.6	0.15	58.8	0.14	2.58	2.29	57.2	0.091	0.213	0.934	4	799
Seneca #20	1	Bloomville	41 03 66 N	83 02 06 W	970916	1541	8.80	20.5	0.05	17.2	0.01	2.59	8.70	56.6	0.035	0.166	1.020	37	506
Seneca #21	21	Bloomville			961016	1511	8.11	16.0	0.01	30.5	0.01	0.18	2.45	39.7	0.010	0.082	0.834	12	587
Seneca #21R	21	Bloomville			961016	1511	8.11	16.0	0.01	29.5	0.00	0.15	2.50	50.9	0.004	0.083	0.775	10	586
Seneca #21	21	Bloomville	40 03 99 N	83 00 86 W	970916	1534	7.20	20.0	0.08	16.7	0.03	2.47	8.70	74.1	0.018	0.161	0.978	50	512
Seneca #22					961016	1542	10.99	17.2	0.10	33.7	0.04	0.59	4.91	73.4	0.005	0.247	1.739	69	726
Seneca #22a	1	Attica			961016	1532	6.57	16.2	0.00	42.4	0.01	0.19	7.38	62.6	0.032	0.170	0.823	16	765
Seneca #22A	1	Attica	41 03 75 N	82 56 37 W	970916	1523	6.00	20.0	0.13	18.9	0.05	2.22	9.24	83.2	0.017	0.181	1.342	63	556
Seneca #23	21	Attica, upstr.			961016	1550	7.46	16.6	0.02	30.3	0.00	-0.03	4.96	71.3	0.003	0.085	0.573	8	795
Seneca #23	21	Attica, upstr.	41 02 69 N	82 51 05 W	970916	1512	6.20	21.0	0.17	19.6	0.05	1.91	9.31	96.9	0.010	0.141	1.288	49	593

Table 11. Locations and site descriptions for Wyandot County samples.

Station ID	Type	Location	Reason for selection
Wyandot # 1	1.2	Sycamore Creek, bridge on TR 13, south of TR 14	Downstream from Sycamore sewage treatment plant. (Wrong directions from county, may have collected a small tributary to Sycamore Creek)
Wyandot # 2	1.0	Sycamore Creek, bridge on SR 231, (section 22)	Upstream from Sycamore sewage treatment plant
Wyandot # 3		Taylor Run, bridge on CR 36c, near CR 136B west of Deunquat	Random Site
Wyandot # 4	3.2	Ditch, SR 67 south of Marseilles	Downstream from poultry house
Wyandot # 5	3.0	Ditch, Bridge on CR 77, west of TR 123a	Upstream of poultry house
Wyandot # 6	4.2	Tributary to Little Tymochtee next to CR 86a (section 2)	Downstream from fields with heavy manure (we may have collected at wrong site i.e.. Little Tymochtee, at CR 71A)
Wyandot # 7	4.0	Tributary to Little Tymochtee at CR 70a, section 27, east of CR 82b	Upstream from fields with heavy manure
Wyandot # 8	3.0	Potato Run, bridge at CR 53 and TR 87	Upstream from pig farm
Wyandot # 9	3.2	Potato Run, bridge on SR 293 south of Wharton	Downstream from pig farm (same site as W-10)
Wyandot # 10	2.0	Potato Run, bridge on SR 293, South of Wharton	Upstream from septic tanks at Wharton
Wyandot # 11	2.2	Potato Run, bridge on CR 47, west of Wharton	Downstream from septic tanks at Wharton
Wyandot # 12	2.0	Little Tymochtee Cr., Bridge on 199, north of CR 44, near County Home	Upstream(?) from county home
Wyandot # 13	2.2	Little Tymochtee Cr., bridge on CR 42 at Lovell	Downstream from county home
Wyandot # 14	4.2	Poverty Run, bridge on TR 106d, north of TR 18a	Downstream from area of heavy manure application
Wyandot # 15	4.0	Poverty Run, bridge on CR 5c, east of TR 105a	Upstream from area of heavy manure application

Figure 6. Location and station identification numbers for sampling sites in Wyandot County.

Table 12. Low flow synoptic survey results for Wyandot County, Heidelberg College Manure Management Grant

County/ Station #	Site Type	Control For Site	Latitude	Longitude	Collection Date	Time	Dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	Temp. Cent.	NH ₃ mg/L	CL mg/L	NO ₂ mg/L	NO ₃ mg/L	SiO ₂ MG/	SO ₄ mg/L	SRP mg/L	TP mg/L	TKN mg/L	SS mg/L	COND µmhos	
Wyandot #1	28		40 58 53 N	83 10 19 W	970905	930	8.60	12.7	0.01	18.8	0.01	1.49	6.93	43.1	0.013	0.099	0.717	9	596	
Wyandot #1R	28		40 58 53 N	83 10 19 W	970905	930	8.60	12.7	0.03	18.7	0.00	1.47	7.01	52.6	0.015	0.091	0.643	8	596	
Wyandot #1	28				971010							NO WATER!								
Wyandot #2	21		40 56 48 N	83 07 89 W	970905	942	7.50	15.1	0.03	30.5	0.00	0.30	2.53	80.6	0.005	0.045	0.463	8	656	
Wyandot #2	21		40 56 52 N	83 07 90 W	971010	917	3.50	16.5	0.03	30.2	0.00	-0.06	3.05	75.9	0.022	0.068	0.411	4	688	
Wyandot #2R	21		40 56 52 N	83 07 90 W	971010	918	3.50	16.5	0.08	29.2	0.00	-0.07	2.95	77.9	0.017	0.069	0.530	3	692	
Wyandot #3	2		40 55 17 N	83 09 06 W	970905	950	8.70	13.3	0.06	37.7	0.00	0.27	11.35	72.2	0.015	0.062	0.493	9	774	
Wyandot #3	2		40 55 27 N	83 09 04 W	971010	924	6.20	15.0	0.08	58.5	0.00	-0.05	8.27	69.8	0.043	0.092	0.350	10	879	
Wyandot #4	5		40 42 20 N	83 23 36 W	970905	1040	8.40	14.3	0.24	24.3	0.01	0.02	3.74	93.2	0.023	0.087	0.887	8	629	
Wyandot #4	5		40 42 15 N	83 23 40 W	971010	1019	4.40	16.0	0.21	34.8	0.00	-0.05	4.96	111.7	0.063	0.114	0.652	15	685	
Wyandot #5	25		40 41 67 N	83 21 99 W	970905	1057	8.70	19.8	0.05	3.5	0.00	0.00	1.80	129.9	0.003	0.044	0.533	34	470	
Wyandot #5	25		40 41 70 N	83 21 99 W	971010	1028	2.90	16.0	0.56	208.6	0.09	2.38	8.02	493.8	0.346	0.641	1.942	74	2070	
Wyandot #6	5		40 43 42 N	83 27 82 W	970905	1130	6.50	16.6	0.05	28.8	0.00	-0.04	1.97	62.7	0.009	0.121	0.945	35	626	
Wyandot #6	5		40 43 47 N	83 27 80 W	971010	1045	3.30	17.0	0.04	124.4	0.00	-0.09	3.83	110.0	0.081	0.417	0.956	42	1129	
Wyandot #7	25		40 44 71 N	83 28 49 W	970905	1120	8.30	16.9	1.22	31.1	0.08	0.81	8.27	53.2	0.184	0.376	2.234	24	830	
Wyandot #7	25		40 44 70 N	83 29 49 W	971010	1053	7.50	16.8	0.29	50.4	0.12	0.78	9.60	265.6	0.295	0.615	1.744	12	1226	
Wyandot #8	24		40 49 11 N	83 26 97 W	970905	1455	11.20	23.1	0.32	2030.0	0.05	0.16	6.34	210.6	0.000	0.182	0.884	61	6580	
Wyandot #8	24				971010							NO WATER!								
Wyandot #9	4		40 50 59 N	83 27 47 W	970905	1505			0.00	118.1	0.00	0.01	0.87	79.2	-0.002	0.096	0.989	15	1080	
Wyandot #9	4				971010							NO WATER!								
Wyandot #10	22				970905	1508	14.00	22.1	0.08	137.3	0.01	0.13	1.61	86.4	0.001	0.079	0.771	13	1180	
Wyandot #10	22		40 50 86 N	83 27 75 W	971010	1349	14.80	22.0	0.28	155.5	0.02	0.01	3.03	137.1	0.016	0.095	1.094	6	1115	
Wyandot #11	2		40 51 70 N	83 29 18 W	970905	1516	11.10	20.9	5.31	149.8	0.12	0.24	5.01	377.1	0.557	0.827	5.728	7	1717	
Wyandot #11	2		40 51 68 N	83 29 14 W	971010	1356	9.20	19.4	6.90	139.8	0.03	0.00	6.37	587.1	1.240	1.504	6.852	8	1895	
Wyandot #12	22		40 52 93 N	83 19 38 W	970905	1540	8.40	18.9	0.06	56.4	0.01	0.88	6.59	380.6	0.029	0.159	1.073	14	1243	
Wyandot #12	22		40 52 90 N	83 19 42 W	971010	1439	5.00	19.0	0.09	55.0	0.00	0.01	8.10	670.5	0.119	0.258	0.826	9	1546	
Wyandot #13	2		40 53 43 N	83 19 78 W	970905	1545	6.40	16.1	0.04	49.9	0.00	0.25	9.10	515.2	0.005	0.086	0.705	10	1442	
Wyandot #13	2		40 53 43 N	83 19 71 W	971010	1444	1.00	18.0	0.00	145.9	0.00	-0.07	12.23	764.9	0.037	0.477	1.736	22	2120	
Wyandot #14	5				970905	1600	10.20	18.7	0.12	95.1	0.11	3.69	4.37	204.3	0.248	0.374	0.498	7	1152	
Wyandot #14	5		40 57 19 N	83 19 16 W	971010	1513	7.60	18.0	0.06	19.8	0.04	1.89	4.39	114.3	0.037	0.072	0.523	4	698	
Wyandot #15	25				970905	1610	10.20	19.6	0.01	18.0	0.02	6.40	4.58	16.8	0.001	0.052	0.432	23	684	
Wyandot #15	25		40 59 07 N		971010	1504	8.90	18.0	0.12	17.4	0.06	5.08	4.92	49.2	0.016	0.065	0.689	20	700	

Quality Control – Field Replicates

The following graphs depict the agreement between field replicates in synoptic surveys conducted by the Water Quality Laboratory of Heidelberg College. These data include replicates from studies for the Richland County SWCD and the Erie County SWCD, as well as samples from this Manure Nutrient Management Study. Replicates were collected by local volunteers in the first two studies and by WQL staff for the manure nutrient management grant.

If there were perfect agreement between replicates, all of the points would fall along a straight line with a slope of 1.0, and intercept of zero and an r-squared of 1.0. Divergence from these values reflects the combined effects of both field precision/field variability in sample collection and laboratory analytical precision.

The close agreement between replicates (i.e., most of the points fall very close to a straight line) indicates that the differences among sampling stations are real differences and not artifacts of collection and analytical problems.

